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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 2.5 – TECHNOLOGY ANALYSIS AND REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION (FINAL VERSION)

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Author(s)	Martijn Rooker (TTC), Sebastian Lorenz (TUD), Volker Waurich (TUD), Clemens Arth (TUG), Manuel Kulzer (HdM), Anastasia Sergeeva (UL), Kaj Helin (VTT), Jerome Perret (HAP), Thomas Howard (HAP), Daniel Röck (PRIN), Pekka Yli-Paunu (KAL)
Contact details of the coordinator	Martijn Rooker, martijn.rooker@tttech.com
Internal Reviewer	Kaj Helin, VTT Markku Pusenius, CREA

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1	Updated the State-of-Art section. New reference list provided	UL, HdM
2	Updated list of non-functional requirements based on D2.3	UL
3.	Specify KPI 4.1	UL
4	Updated chapter 2.4 to differentiate the main underlying concepts	UL, HdM
5	Updated technology analysis chapter 2.2.1	HAP
6	Update of Executive Summary	TTC
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Executive summary

In this document, the final work performed in Task 2.2 – Technology Analysis & Requirement Specifications since the submission of the previous deliverable (i.e., D2.2 – Technology Analysis & Requirements Specification (first version)), will be summarized. This mainly includes the updates performed to this deliverable compared to its predecessor, mainly focusing on the updates of the Technology Analysis, Use Case details, Requirements and the definition of the baselines for the identified KPIs. Once again, this deliverable works on the results of deliverable D2.4 (which is the successor of D2.1) and will provide an updated detailed overview of the different scenarios identified within the said deliverable. This content of this deliverable is the final version and will provide the final basis for the evaluation of the work performed within the project.

The deliverable starts with an updated overview of the state-of-the-art of the different technical and research domains that are targeted within the THEIA^{XR} project and that will help us towards the final results of the project. This information is partially based on the state-of-the-art information provided in the project proposal, but is now more extended and described in detail. Compared to deliverable D2.2, it has been extended with new input that has been acquired during the first phase of the project, where new findings have been established and new topics have arisen that were not identified at the beginning of the project, thereby demonstrating the advancements that have been made within the project. The analysis focuses on topics like XR technologies, human-machine interaction, co-design, privacy, etc.

This deliverable also provides more details about the use case definitions, including new findings that have been performed during the first phase of the project. At the beginning of the projects, the use cases were defined mainly based on expectations from the use case leads and technical partners. At this stage in the project, much feedback has been gathered, among other from operators from the targeted machines, that have given the consortium a much deeper insight in the operation of these machines and the requests from the operators. These will be reflected in the updates of the use cases and the scenario descriptions. The use cases are referenced from deliverable D2.4 and describe the different activities in the scenarios of the use cases. It provides a more detailed overview of the scenarios and where the XR technologies come into play. Furthermore, the deliverable identifies a final set of requirements for the different technologies and for the use cases, based on the earlier defined requirements and the experiences the partners have acquired in the first phase of the project. Modifications, deletions or additions of requirements are described in the respective sections. These requirements are separated into functional, non-functional and technical requirements and are defined for the individual use cases and the technologies.

Finally, the deliverable also focuses on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined during the proposal phase. These KPIs are the basis for the evaluation of the final results of the project. One of the most important aspects of the KPIs are the baselines against which they will be evaluated. Within this updated deliverable, an updated version of the baselines is provided that will highlight this aspect. Certain baselines have been identified in an earlier state of the project and are still valid, whereas other baselines are very hard or sometimes impossible to define in advance. These baselines are highlighted explicitly, and it is elaborated how these KPIs will be validated based on their respective baselines.

As mentioned before, this is the final version of deliverable D2.5 and is the basis for the final evaluation of the developments in the project. It will be referenced and used at the end of the project during the evaluation phase and explained how the defined KPIs are fulfilled within the project, referring to the identified baselines.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable summarizes the work that has been carried out as part of Tasks 2.2 – Technology Analysis & Requirements Specifications, including the updates after the first version of this deliverable (i.e., deliverable D2.2 – Technology Analysis & Requirements Specification (first version)). The current deliverable covers the final use case definition, requirements and baselines identified during the project. These inputs are the final basis for the updated developments in the technical work packages and the evaluations to be performed during the rest of the project. At the end of the project, it will be evaluated which requirements are fulfilled and how the KPIs are established, based on the identified baselines.

Deliverable D2.5 is divided into four different parts. The first part provides a state-of-the-art technology and methodology analysis about the different solutions targeted within the THEIA^{XR} project. Compared to deliverable D2.2, this section has been extended with new findings of technologies or methodologies that have been identified to be of further interest to the results of the project.

The second part of the deliverable is based on the outcomes of Task 2.1 and what is reported in deliverable D2.4, which is the updated version of deliverable D2.1. This includes the specification of the requirements of the three use cases that will be developed as part of the project. Deliverable D2.4 provides the final definitions of each use case, and this deliverable unfolds those definitions to produce a set of requirements that will be developed in the technical work packages (WP3 – WP5). Furthermore, the overarching use case steps described in 3.1.1, 3.1.2 and 3.1.3 of this document provided the main tasks of interest for which the context of use was studied in T3.1 and the interaction concepts are being developed in T3.2.

The requirements are defined in the third part of the deliverable. Three main sets of requirements are defined within the scope of this work: functional, non-functional and technical requirements. These cover the requirements from a user-perspective and that is why they are specified in tight connection with the use cases. The technical requirements are covering internal functionalities and technicalities of the solutions.

The last part of the deliverable further elaborates the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and their baseline performance. These KPIs are going to form the basis of evaluation criteria for the success of the project and cover the project objectives.

2 Technology Analysis

THEIA^{XR} proposes the creation of XR technologies and methodologies to provide information to the human operator to make the invisible visible respectively the non-perceivable perceivable. As such, it will investigate different technologies capable of presenting data to the human operator, be it visual, acoustic, or haptic. The target is to advance Extended Reality (XR) technologies and bring them into the domain of off-highway machinery, or more precisely, into the operation area of the human operator for controlling the machinery (i.e., the cabin or the remote working station). The challenge is how to capture the data and translate it into information perceivable for the human operator.

To achieve those ambitions, THEIA^{XR} aims to build upon several key technical solutions and, through the collective work carried out during the project, to move beyond the state-of-the-art. The following subsections present those key technologies and the current state-of-the-art in each one of them.

2.1 Extended Reality (XR)

Extended reality (XR), sometimes referred to cross reality, is an umbrella term, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and mixed reality (MR). VR is a completely computer-generated environment with no real-world aspects included while AR and MR are a mix of real world and virtual aspects. The difference between AR and MR is the immersivity. In AR, the virtual aspects do not need to necessarily blend with the real world, while in MR the goal is to completely blend the virtual aspects into the real world. This is illustrated in the figure below [1][2].

Figure 1: XR, VR, AR and MR [1]

The further step to improve the cross-platform compatibility in XR (and VR in particular) has been done by Khronos, who released the OpenXR¹ standard in 2019. The project has been supported by the majority of the companies involved in XR. OpenXR places itself between the development platforms and the final hardware on which to run the application. It can be supported by game engines, it can be used barebone by invoking its API, and it can also be used for WebXR projects. The standard is available for free to all the manufacturers that decide to expose their systems to OpenXR APIs, and in the last few years more and more devices have already received support for it. To name a few, Valve Index, HTC Vive visors, Meta Quest visors, MagicLeap devices are now all compatible with OpenXR. This means that the developer only must select OpenXR as the target platform for the build (together with a few other specs such as the OS and the CPU architecture), and the project is ready to be compiled.

The AR platforms for developing projects are strictly bound to the mainstream computing platforms available today. The first SDK to be released was ARKit by Apple for its iPhone and iPad devices. The kit was released²

¹ <https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>

² <https://www.techrepublic.com/article/apples-arkit-everything-the-pros-need-to-know/>

in June 2017. ARCore³, an evolution of the existing project Tango that has been adapted for Android smartphones and tablets. On the other hand, Microsoft has been struggling in the last few years to attract developers, since Windows Phone has been officially removed from the market and their only major strength is having no competitors to their physical product, the HoloLens 2⁴.

While the AR environment is dominated by a few incumbents, the VR world suffers from the opposite problem, where a wide fragmentation of ecosystems follows a variety of VR vendors. This situation gives a lot of choice to consumers, but on the other hand it makes it harder for developers to reach out a large user base and to quickly adapt to new technologies. Among the vendors, to name a few, we can find Acer, HP, Valve, HTC, Meta, MagicLeap, Varjo, Samsung and more (an extensive list is given in section “List of XR devices”). Naturally, every headset comes with its own drivers and SDKs, such as OpenVR⁵ for SteamVR devices, HTC Wave⁶ for HTC devices (and some other third parties), Oculus SDK for what are now the visors owned by Meta.

Unity, for example, provides a “Unity XR” framework, that lets developers program game logic, scripting, and scenery, only once and then choose the platform for which they want to build. The framework drastically reduces the complexity of the overall development, as the only things that need to be tinkered with are the management of the different controllers and the build configurations for the different platforms (see Figure 2). Nonetheless, some drawbacks are still present, the most important one being that the implementation is strictly dependent on the game engine (in this case, Unity). Another drawback is that all the specific implementations of the SDKs must be present and configured in the project, and this can lead to several problems such as a larger project size, compatibility issues and conflicts among the different SDKs. To make an example, SteamVR tries to configure a specific component of Unity XR, called XR Interaction Toolkit, in a way that is not compatible with the other SDKs. The only way to fix the issue is to have two versions of the XR Interaction Toolkit package, an official one for all the packages and then another one in another folder that has been specifically configured for SteamVR. Finally, it might be necessary to add multiple platform-specific components to the Unity scene for every platform to work correctly.

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ARCore>

⁴ <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2017/08/microsoft-was-leading-the-world-in-ar-now-its-at-risk-of-being-left-behind/>

⁵ <https://github.com/ValveSoftware/openvr>

⁶ <https://developer.vive.com/eu/wave/>

Unity XR Tech Stack

Figure 2: A representation of the current Unity XR stack (Source Unity⁷).

OpenXR places itself between the development platforms and the final hardware on which to run the application. It can be supported by game engines, it can be used barebone by invoking its API, and it can also be used for WebXR projects.

Before OpenXR: Applications and engines needed separate proprietary code for each device on the market.

OpenXR provides a single cross-platform, high-performance API between applications and all conformant devices.

Figure 3: Application development pipeline before and after using OpenXR (Source: Khronos⁸)

With OpenXR, all the tools that were available before, remain available (i.e., Unity’s ARFoundation, XR Interaction Toolkit, as well as third-party software such as SteamAudio). What changes is the backend translation layer that is run at compile time, where OpenXR is used instead of the built-in layer such as Unity XR native provider (see Figure 3).

In Appendix 1, we attached a list of the most recent or otherwise notable XR headsets. The information gathered here is general specification easily available online and the list is non-exclusive in both headsets and their features.

Traditionally, haptic feedback is split between tactile (i.e., stimulation of the skin) and kinesthetic (i.e., stimulation of the muscles and tendons), the latter being often referred to as “force-feedback”. In the last

⁷ <https://unity.com/>

⁸ https://www.khronos.org/api/index_2017/openxr

decade, both modalities of haptic feedback have entered our daily lives. The tactile modality is present in our smartphones and tablets as vibrotactile feedback. The kinesthetic modality is used for example in cars, for lane-following and brake-by-wire. Those examples demonstrate an almost invisible and well accepted implementation of Augmented Reality (AR), but for very simple, one-dimensional functions.

In the context of Virtual Reality (VR), vibro-tactile feedback is integrated in all controllers associated with head-mounted displays (HMD). The main use is to signal a condition of proximity with a zone of interest or with an obstacle. Since the vibration alone can only convey very crude information, the user depends on visual cues displayed over the 3D representation of the controller in addition to the haptic signal. Kinesthetic feedback is rarely implemented, because of the high cost of the hardware, and only in a professional context, with two main applications: VR-based training for healthcare [1], and assembly simulation for industry [3].

A very important concept for kinesthetic feedback, introduced as early as in the 1990s in the context of telerobotic manipulation, is that of “virtual fixtures” [4]. A virtual fixture is usually described as a constraint in Cartesian space, which is enforced by the haptic device during the interaction with the user. A typical example is a sliding hinge along the axis of a drill, which helps the human operator keep the alignment, therefore preventing damage to the tool. Virtual fixtures may combine constraints in movement and force, like keeping the orientation with respect to a predefined surface while applying a constant force (e.g., sanding operation).

It is important to address the specific case of force feedback joysticks, insofar as they may appear as a natural extension of existing controls in off-highway machinery. It is worth noting that force feedback joysticks have applications in video gaming, but that the commercial offer has always remained very limited: Mainly Microsoft's Sidewinder and Logitech's G940. This is partly due to the existence of blocking patents (mainly held by Immersion Systems), and partly to low demand. In the professional field, there are only a few small players, such as Sensodrive (at the prototype stage) and Brunner (specialized in flight simulators). Unfortunately, these products have a fixed and restrictive ergonomics, which does not offer any freedom in the design of the haptic modalities.

Sound is also an important aspect of perceived space and objects. Traditional 3D surround sound systems like 5.1 or 7.1 do not work well with XR, however. The traditional model assumes fixed positions of speakers, such as front centre and rear left, but with XR the user can yaw, pitch and roll their head freely which needs to be considered if an accurate immersion is to be accomplished. The research on this subject is ongoing and evolving, but there are already some providers of 3D audio plugins and solutions. However, the major breakthrough and consensus on how to do 3D audio is yet to come [57][47].

2.1.1 Progress beyond State of the Art

In the future, more and more vendors are making their devices compatible with OpenXR, they are often making them available in “compatibility mode”, rather than making every feature of the hardware available also with OpenXR. Varjo devices, for example, can run OpenXR applications, but if specific device features are needed (such as the image pass-through, hand recognition, or marker recognition), the developer is forced to make use of the proprietary Varjo SDK and remove support for OpenXR.

Kinesthetic feedback has shown very good performance and acceptability but has been limited either to the office environment (telerobotics) or to a single degree-of-freedom (steering wheel). There is a huge potential for the implementation of virtual fixtures in the THEIA^{XR} applications like snow grooming or container handling, but they call for a compact and sturdy multi-dimensional force-feedback device. Our goal in the project is to develop a mechanical concept for such a device and build a mock-up that can be evaluated in the field.

To the best of our knowledge, although it has been extensively studied in the context of wheeled road vehicles [5] and their simulators [6], haptic feedback has never been applied to the off-highway vehicle domain. Force feedback through the steering wheel appears to be an effective means for e.g., assisting steering [7], lane-keeping [8], and the safe manoeuvring of vehicles with attached trailers [9]. Tactile feedback has demonstrated effectiveness in vehicle navigation assistance [6], obstacle avoidance [10] and speed control [11]. This hints at a strong potential for using haptics not only in off-highway vehicle tool controls, but also in the steering elements.

2.2 Human-Machine Interaction

Digitalization and automation technology allows mobile machines to perform more activities at a higher level of autonomy [12][13] and with a higher level of data-driven assistance than conventional machines. Advanced machine and environment sensing technology, automated context-aware controls [13][14] and digital machine, process and environment modelling, change the content that must be provided by human-machine interfaces. As 100% reliable automation is not possible nor feasible soon, automation supervision still requires human involvement as a control and corrective instance [15][16][17]. Implementing ever more complex digital worlds containing data, simulations, assistance functions, plans, processes, etc., pushes display-based terminal interfaces in operation work environments to their limits. Restrictions in space and interaction for using display terminals lead to over complex UI architectures resulting in high interaction workload and distraction.

This work recognizes **human-machine interaction** as activities of retrieving (e.g., extracting system state from user interface) and giving information (e.g., controlling user interface or machine) in the context of operation tasks with many concurring goals such as safety, productivity and efficiency. Involved activities of information acquisition, information analysis, decision-making, action selection, and action implementation utilize knowledge and skills to different extents (see. Cognitive work continuum, skill, knowledge, rule-based behaviour [18]). Further there are automation-sensitive attitudes that affect application and change of competencies.

Maintaining situation awareness and handling complexity might become major **issues** as systems become more complex, intransparent and dynamic. Endsley and Kiris [19], Lee and Seppelt [20], Chen and Barnes [21] provide a good overview on a variety of human factors evolved in digitally advanced machine operation, covering **situation awareness, spatial ability, attentional control, deskillng, compliance, adaptation, workload and trust in automation**. However, the factors underlying these challenges are complex and interacting as they are consequences of complex human behaviour in complex systems and situations. Many of these factors and issues are directly or indirectly linked to automation design and user interface design, task and environmental contexts, and the operators' cognitive resources, capabilities, and states.

Therefore, **maintaining situation awareness** [17] is a key criterion and motivation to improve HMIs regarding their current design philosophies, strategies, and technologies. Situation awareness (SA) is necessary for informed and reliable decision-making. The earliest and most widely used formal definition of SA describes it as “the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future”[22]. SA therefore involves perceiving critical factors in the environment (level 1 SA), understanding what those factors mean, particularly when integrated together in relation to the person's goals (level 2), and at the highest level an understanding of what will happen with the system soon (level 3). These higher levels of SA allow people to function in a timely and effective manner, even with very complex and challenging tasks. As it is a central activity in machine operation, operators often utilize skill-based behaviour that is based on a long record of experience, analytical, reasoning and situation assessment skills [17]. State of the art research already propose frameworks, concepts, and strategies to fundamentally reimagine HMI design. Approaches that are linked to XR technologies are the concept of **natural user interfaces (NUI)**, **multimodal interaction (MI)** and **adaptive user interfaces (AUI)**.

2.2.1 NUI – Natural User Interfaces

Natural User Interfaces (NUIs) are computer interfaces that enable users to interact with machines more intuitively and human-likely, without the need for special training, complex instructions, or overly artificial artefacts. Extended reality interaction could benefit from NUI approaches as using gestures, direct manipulation (of real or virtual objects), facial and body expressions, voice commands, and other non-verbal cues have the potential to ease the use of complex interfaces. One of the critical benefits of NUIs is that they can help to bridge the gap between people and machines, making technology more accessible to a broader range of users. By enabling users to interact with machines more naturally and intuitively. NUIs can help

reduce the learning curve of using complex software and hardware systems. Another key benefit of NUIs is that they can help to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of machine operation. By leveraging the power of natural communication modalities, such as speech recognition and gesture recognition, NUIs can enable users to perform tasks more quickly and accurately than they would be able to with traditional input devices such as keyboards and mice. This can be particularly valuable in high-pressure situations, where speed and accuracy are critical. NUIs can be classified into three main categories: gesture-based, speech-based, and touch-based. Gesture-based interfaces allow users to interact with computers using hand or body gestures. Speech-based interfaces allow users to interact with computers using natural language commands. Touch-based interfaces allow users to interact with computers using multi-touch screens or other tactile inputs. NUIs can make computing systems more immersive and engaging, enhancing the user's experience. Finally, NUIs have the potential to transform the way we interact with computers, opening new possibilities for collaboration and communication which is one of the projects main goals. However, there is little experience and practice in implementing NUI interaction in digital industrial machine operation environments, even though haptic manipulations and feedback are already important in manual machine operation.

Researchers point out that natural interaction interfaces influence user experience, and it should be designed to identify user requests during interaction accurately and to provide the user with intuitive means of interaction with low cognitive effort [23]. Some researchers have begun exploring the potential of interaction within XR environments using gestures. Chessa and Noceti reveal that user interaction with virtual content involving human hand gestures has resulted in more successful performance indicators (such as speed, error rate, the natural quality of interaction), compared to a virtual hand avatar [24]. Bai states that, while interaction with 3D motion-based free-hand movements without markers is more intuitive and natural than 2D touch-based interaction with depth perception, this may create limitations for 3D motion-based interaction [25].

2.2.2 Multimodal, augmenting information presentation

Multimodal information presentation refers to enhancing the bandwidth of our information processing capacity by utilizing many perception channels. Even though visual perception can handle complex information, using vibrotactile or acoustic perception can improve the quality of information presentation, support coordinative functions, attention management, detection, and evaluation reliability. Several authors have argued that to achieve these goals, “different display and control requirements cannot be arbitrarily assigned to auditory and speech channels” (e.g., [26]). Multimodal interaction is not a static approach. Instead, it is more effective when combination of information modalities is based on situative requirements.

Visual information presentation is heavily emphasized in today’s interface designs. For the most part, these interfaces rely on foveal vision, which seems appropriate for the presentation of complex graphics and, in general, for conveying large amounts of detailed information. A related advantage of visual information is its potential for permanent presentation, which affords delayed and prolonged attending. Also, vision does not require us to be as close to a (potentially dangerous) source of information as, for example, taste or smell. Current interfaces make deliberate use of peripheral vision to a much lesser extent. While the two channels – foveal and peripheral vision – do not, in the strict sense, represent separate modalities, they are associated with different options and constraints. Peripheral vision is well suited for detecting motion, luminance changes, and the appearance of new objects. In contrast, foveal vision supports the recognition of objects or details. Peripheral vision is assumed to determine the destination of our next saccade. In that sense, it represents an early orientation mechanism that can be utilized by designers to help operators attend to a relevant location or critical information at the right time. A potential problem with peripheral visual feedback is that the visual field changes dynamically in response to contextual factors. With increasing foveal task loading, for example, visual attention begins to focus on information in the centre of a display at the expense of information presented in peripheral vision – a phenomenon called “attentional narrowing”.

The auditory channel differs from vision along several dimensions. First, it is omnidirectional, thus allowing for information to be picked up from any direction. Secondly, auditory information presentation is transient.

This potential limitation is compensated for by a longer short-term storage of auditory (as opposed to visual) information so that it can be processed with some delay.

Finally, since it is impossible for us to “close our ears,” auditory displays tend to be intrusive and are often reserved for alerting functions.

A currently underutilized channel for presenting information is the **haptic sense**. Haptic sensory information can take the form of either tactile or kinaesthetic cues. Tactile feedback is presented to the skin through force, texture, vibration, and thermal sensations. Kinaesthetic, or proprioceptive, cues convey information about body position, motion, and the forces acting on the body. Sense of touch shares several properties with the auditory channel. Most importantly, cues presented via these two modalities are transient. Also, like vision and hearing, touch allows for the concurrent presentation and extraction of several dimensions, such as frequency and amplitude, in the case of vibrotactile cues.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of each of the above sensory channels for information presentation depends heavily on context. It is affected by the mental state of a person and by interactions and interference between modalities. For example, the speed of detection and response to different modalities varies with a person’s state. It appears to shift from the visual to the auditory channel if subjects are in state of aversive arousal. Another important cross modally phenomenon is visual dominance, which counteracts the natural tendency of humans to orient their attention to stimuli in the auditory and tactile modality. Visual dominance is observed when visual stimuli appear at about the same frequency and/or are of the same relevance to the person as the other cues.

2.2.3 Adaptable and adaptive user interfaces

Advanced digitized and automated machines often go along with an increased information range and complexity. Communicating or displaying all available information simultaneously to the operator is impractical and may result in overly nested screen layouts and sub-page architectures. The approach of interface adaptability aims at providing the right information in the right form at the right time. This approach involves two stages.

Firstly, adaptable or customizable interfaces adjust their properties based on human input. Secondly, adaptive interfaces employ automated adaptation, which requires context awareness [27][28]. It is called mixed-initiative if both entities can control adaptation [29][30].

HMI adaptation has received extensive attention, research [31], development [32], and testing [33]. A HMI that can adapt to situations, system properties, or individual capabilities, states, requirements, or preferences may offer the potential for improved user experience, user performance, usability, intuitive, and workload. HMI adaptability that can consider the operators' proficiency in operation tasks may also facilitate their learning curve.

In the context of THEIA^{XR}, adaptability could support operators in familiarizing themselves with novel XR interaction forms. Adapting their extent or blending with conventional means of interaction allows for a gradual involvement in the operators' monitoring and control routines instead of presenting all new HMI at once. This could lead to limitations, including misfit, user cognitive disruption, lack of prediction, and lack of explanation that undermine the expected benefits. While several adaptation techniques exist for desktop UIs, they may not be suitable for mobile machines due to computational constraints, limited interaction techniques, high user workload, and dynamic environmental factors. Navigating through complex adaptation processes can be cumbersome and time-consuming, especially with lengthy processes, thus necessitating innovative interaction techniques for HMI adaptation [34].

2.2.4 Interaction Technology

Input devices provide the user with means to enter data in interactive systems. Generally speaking, an input device is a sensor that registers changes in the user behaviour, such as touch gestures. Output technologies include technologies that can generate responses to user input. An example is the display of a change in temperature using an LCD display.

The systematizations of Dumas et al. (2009) [35] and Schmid and Maier (2017) [36] also divide into input and output. This division initially makes the systematization more complex. However, input and feedback can

each be selected separately. At first glance, this does not make sense for all interaction technologies. For example, a touchscreen has both input and output functions. In addition, all haptic input devices with moving components have intrinsic feedback: For example, whether a rotary switch is turned on or off is noticed by proprioception and pressure on the fingers. Despite these circumstances, a clear separation into input and output should be made. By the conscious separation many combination possibilities of inputs and outputs can be tried out. This differentiation allows the feedback to be examined and evaluated separately from the input. The output technologies were classified according to modality. After reviewing the collected output technologies, three major themes could be identified (see Figure 4): Visual output, tactile/haptic output, and auditory output. Feedback variants via the other modalities, such as olfactory or gustatory feedback, were grouped under "Other" because they have hardly any relevance so far. Even "fancy" technologies such as biofeedback, which is based on a combination of visual and interoceptive feedback, are also assigned to this category. "Social feedback" falls out of the classification grid because it is already a rating of a combined feedback (mostly auditory and visual). It was nevertheless included to visualize the range of possibilities.

Figure 4: Example sheets of a library of interaction technologies, clustered regarding capabilities in information mapping, interaction and suitability for input and output means (own visualization)

2.2.5 Progress beyond State of the Art

There are many frameworks in human-machine interaction, human-robot interaction, and human-computer interaction. Three major ones are described in this deliverable. However, these frameworks need more applicability within detailed discussions in complex real-world machine user interfaces. In THEIA^{XR}, these frameworks will be composed to inform our design procedures and decisions. Further, common development tools will be extended to fit the unique requirements of XR interfaces with a strong focus on multimodality and prototyping-based development processes. Transparent and detailed documentation of our procedure, toolkits, and decisions will provide valuable insights to evaluate these frameworks. We also plan to exemplarily extend them to increase usability and applicability for HMI designers and developers. THEIA^{XR} is implementing and combining technology not seen before in machine operation environments with regards to acceptable costs and benefits for operation performance and safety. Benefits of multimodal interaction have been promoted long ago, but besides “natural” (system-based), multimodality, no real fundamental exploration of ways to involve all modalities in the context of today's technological possibilities has been reported for mobile machinery. THEIA^{XR} will comprehensively and methodologically complement modalities for enhanced perception and evaluation. In HMI/HCI research, there is a gap between theoretical modelling and frameworks and the actual complexity of decisions in machine HMIs. The project documentation will provide an abstracted User-system model required to implement multimodal and adaptable HMIs.

2.3 Off-Highway Mobile Machinery

Off-Highway vehicles, more often called mobile machinery, are considered being any type of vehicle, which is purpose build for driving on rough terrain and not only on automotive highways. Normally, they are intended for use on steep or uneven grounds and include, among others, machines for construction, agriculture, forest, cargo handling, but also some of the municipal vehicles. One of the first off-highway or off-road vehicles was developed in the early 1900s, which was called the Kégresse Track [37]. It was developed by Adolphe Kégresse who worked for the Czar Nicholas II of Russia between 1906 and 1916. The system was a caterpillar track that could be fitted to a car or truck, making it capable of traversing over rough or soft ground. The second world war saw a large increase in off-highway vehicles, which finally resulted in many different domains for which specific off-highway vehicles were developed and deployed. In the following subsections, the domains targeted by the THEIA^{XR} project will be introduced including the machinery that will be used in the designated use cases.

2.3.1 XR-Applications in Construction Machinery

While XR and AR technologies were used exclusively for marketing purposes and not ready for use prototypes for a long time, there are now several series products that use XR/AR technologies. In principle, there are currently three main use cases for XR technologies in the construction machines sector, as illustrated in Figure 5 (From left to Right: 1) Wacker Neuson Smart Glasses for remote maintenance and expert consulting with live video stream⁹, 2) Doosan's display of a transparent shovel on a wheel loader¹⁰ and 3) Trimble SiteVision AR-System to display digital terrain models¹¹:

- Support for model-based earthmoving that integrate digital terrain models, 3D machine control systems and survey equipment
- Remote maintenance applications where maintenance and service work on a construction machine is supported by AR devices.
- Safety functions that contribute to the expansion of visibility and improvement of the perception of the environment.

Figure 5: Three applications of XR/AR technology in the domains of construction machines

The potential for XR-technology in construction machinery goes far beyond the current state of the art. In particular, the support for model-based earthworks can benefit from XR-technology. Model-based earthworks refer to the usage of digital terrain models which are used to create the target design surface without any additional surveying. The construction machine itself is equipped with RTK-GNSS and motion sensors to position the tool with cm-precision. The operator sees an indication if the machine tool is at the desired height.

With the help of XR-Technology and additional sensors, the Human-Machine-Interface can be enhanced to get a much more intuitive representation of the design model aligned with the real environment.

Because these so-called 3D-machine –control systems are supplier products, their HMI is not seamlessly integrated into the cabin design. A modern excavator cabin might be equipped with up to 4 separate displays: the machine main display, the 3D-machine control system, a camera-monitor to see several rear- and side-

⁹ <https://wackerneusongroup.com/konzern/innovation>

¹⁰ <https://im-mining.com/2021/03/08/doosan-launches-transparent-bucket-system-wheel-loaders/>

¹¹ <https://www.sitech-austria.at/produkte/software-it/trimble-sitevision>

facing cameras and a tool management system. With the help of XR-technology, a highly integrated HMI can feature all these features in a uniform way.

2.3.2 XR applications in Snow grooming

Snow grooming is the process of creating a desired snow surface for dedicated winter sport activities. This includes mainly alpine skiing, cross country (classical and skating style), freestyle, tobogganing and trail grooming for snow mobile runs.

A snow groomer is a mobile machinery, traditionally driven by a Diesel engine which drives a hydrostatic powertrain. Even though vehicles powered by electric batteries or hydrogen are about to start entering the market, we simplify here the concept description on the as of today predominant diesel-driven vehicles.

Figure 6: Principle of a snow groomer powertrain ©PRINOTH

Key task of an operator is to create the desired surface by using the blade and the tiller as main tools. The traction of the vehicle is created by the tracks, in some configurations supported by a winch.

The blade in front of the vehicle is used, depending on the condition of the slope, to push snow on the desired spot to build the topography on the slope or in daily slope maintenance to break the first layer of snow and start to roll this snow along the radius of the blade. That process allows to soften and mix the snow with air to reduce the energy effort of the tiller.

The tracks contribute by crushing bigger chunks with the crosslinks when driving over it. Finally, the tiller completes the snow processing by tilling the snow with the teeth on the tiller shaft, distributing the snow-air mix over the full width of the tiller housing and compress with the finisher mat at the end. This compression is to get out the air again and leaving a compact layer of snow. Low air content in the snow supports the physical process of sintering, which is the last step of setting up a long-lasting and resistant slope. This process requires time; therefore, a shift of grooming should be considered based on the opening time for the slope. To adapt to the different conditions like ambient temperature, snow temperature, density and water content, the operator can adjust the tiller regarding cutting depth, tiller rotation speed and pressure applied. State of the art technology allow the operator to control and interact with the vehicle in CAN-controlled systems and give permanent feedback on the chosen settings and status of vehicle sub-systems, such as engine, tiller, and winch.

As trend for efficiency, digital systems like telemetric based fleet management and snow measurement are getting more and more common in ski resort. Specially the knowledge of the amount of snow and where to bring it is key for a successful slope management. The system used GNSS in combination with RTK technology, identifying the position of the vehicle to an accuracy of 2-3 cm (see Figure 7). This position is compared to a predefined terrain model, which can be based on the ground scan of the area or a computer-generated target geometry on the slope or snow terrain park. The offset below the vehicle represents the amount of snow.

Figure 7: Principle of GNSS RTK snow measurement ©PRINOTH

To bring the operator in the position to act proactively, a measurement not only under the vehicle but also underneath the blade is key. So, he can identify based on a color-coded heat map of the last recorded snow height data decide how to work with the snow and distribute it accordingly.

As projection of future development towards workload reduction and efficiency increase, several technologies offer promising possibilities for assistance or (part-)autonomous operation. Visualization concepts like Head-up-displays, head-mounted-displays or projection technologies are known from other industries and could bring also benefit for the snow grooming operator. Further the sensor technologies like Radar, LIDAR, camera systems etc. are potential foundation for a better surrounding representation which can lead in a better task execution.

2.3.3 XR Applications in Container Handling

In logistic applications, XR and AR technologies have been utilized until now mainly for marketing and training purposes. Only in a couple of applications AR technology has been utilized to help the driver in container positioning. XR and AR technologies can be effectively utilized for container handling machines to enhance their efficiency, safety, and overall operational productivity when the machine is driven from on board cabin or remotely controlled from the control centre. In automated/semi-automated machines, remote control is needed for exception handling or, in some use cases it is a part of the normal work cycle.

Here are some ways to leverage XR and AR in container handling machines:

- XR technology can enable remote operation of container handling machines like reachstacker. Using XR headsets or power walls, operators can control the machines from a central location with good productivity and safely. Additionally, XR can be used for training remote operators by simulating real-world scenarios and providing interactive guidance.
- AR can overlay important information, such as container details, load weight, and handling instructions, onto the operator's field of view. This real-time data visualization improves situational awareness and allows remote operators and drivers to make decisions quickly.
- Spatial Mapping and Object Detection: XR and AR can leverage sensors and cameras to create accurate spatial maps of the surroundings. This mapping data can be used for object detection and collision avoidance, helping operators manoeuvre the machines safely and efficiently.
- AR can provide step-by-step instructions overlaid on the operator's view, guiding them through complex workflows. For example, visual cues can be displayed to indicate the optimal path for moving containers, minimizing errors, and maximizing productivity.
- XR can be used for maintenance and troubleshooting tasks. By overlaying digital information onto the physical components of the machine, technicians can access detailed maintenance instructions, identify faulty parts, and receive real-time feedback during repairs.
- XR simulations can help optimize container handling operations by allowing operators and planners to simulate different scenarios. By visualizing the impact of changes in layout, equipment positioning, or workflow, stakeholders can make decisions to improve efficiency.
- XR can facilitate collaborative work among multiple operators or teams. They can share a common virtual workspace, where they can see and interact with the same virtual objects or data. This enables better coordination and communication during the complex container handling tasks.

- XR technologies can capture and analyse data from container handling machines, providing insights into operational performance. This data can be used for identifying bottlenecks, optimizing workflows, and implementing predictive maintenance strategies.

Figure 8: Correct landing position of the container showed with AR

By tagging containers, a terminal operator can read the tags as the goods are placed into a shipping container and confirm exactly what is in each container, and that it matches what is supposed to be in it. This can be accomplished by staging the goods and reading the tags via antennas installed to container handling machines. The active tag might also have a location transmitter in it, so it can communicate its location. This information can be added to remote control video screens which helps remote operator to verify that the correct container, container is not opened and evaluate how to handle the container.

2.3.4 Progress beyond State of the Art

Within the off-highway domain, the usage of XR is not that common yet. The aim of the THEIA^{XR} project is to investigate how XR technologies can support the human (remote) operator of certain off-highway mobile machines, to support them in their activities and improve their work and the safety. Within the project, the three abovementioned domains will be targeted, all three facing different difficulties for improving the work performance and ultimately, the safety of the operator, machine, and its surroundings.

This will result in technologies that will become the future User Interface between the human operator (either direct in the cabin or remotely) for controlling these kinds of machines. The technologies will enable to make the unperceivable perceivable to the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can still focus on the task at hand. The (industrial) use case partners will make mobile machinery available where these technologies can be integrated and will be tested in real-life scenarios, pushing these technologies to their limited in harsh environments.

2.4 Transdisciplinary Co-Design Approach

2.4.1 Transdisciplinary Research

Transdisciplinarity is increasingly considered to be the key to facing societal and environmental challenges of the modern world and developing technology for complex sociotechnical systems [78][79]. Transdisciplinary research (TDR) is most commonly defined and characterized by the involvement of both academic and non-academic actors in co-creative processes [79][80], similar to the involvement of users and stakeholders in the human-centred design (HCD) methodology [81], which is widely established in human-computer interaction (HCI) research and XR application development [82][83]. Recent studies also underline the superior economic performance of companies applying core concepts of human-centred design [39]. However, in traditional HCD, the prioritization of requirements and the design and selection of solutions commonly remains reserved for the design and engineering teams [84]. TDR in contrast empowers non-academic actors from society through co-design or similar processes [79], considering them experts for their domains of knowledge [42] and elevating them to full partners at eye-level with the design team[79].

2.4.2 Co-Design Methodology

Co-design, a key methodology of transdisciplinary research, has long been known and used in the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) community under the term of participatory design [85], which originated in the 1970s in Scandinavia [42][41] and has mainly seen use in service design [43]. The application of co-design has been observed to provide many benefits to service design projects, such as increased speed to market, increased user satisfaction, improved efficiency and effectiveness of products [43]. Transformative science has elaborated the fundamental concept of co-design as a scientific approach [80]. The basic idea is that people who are influenced by certain research should be involved in almost all scientific processes, from defining the research question to reflecting on the results. Finding and defining the research questions are part of the so-called co-design phase. Co-production is the joint activity of developing a solution through multiple evaluations and iterations. And finally, the co-evaluation phase is the documentation of process results and their joint interpretation and reflection. The basic idea is that a broad interdisciplinary in the research team is built up. This team is supplemented by all persons who are directly or indirectly affected by the research and its results.

2.4.3 Progress beyond State of the Art

While transdisciplinary research is currently mainly found in education, urban planning, sustainability and environmental sciences [89], it has not gained much traction in XR application development or engineering so far. Similarly, co-design has seen success in service design and in the public sector [43][86], but there is little evidence of its use in XR and engineering contexts. Especially in engineering domains, there in fact appears to be a certain hesitancy to adopt human-centred procedures [87][88]. The successful exploration of a transdisciplinary co-design approach would provide a template for adapting and improving this process in future technical research and innovation projects. Furthermore, the perception of co-design by all involved actors and its application for the design for positive user experience have not been studied before and will be of particular interest in this project. The perception of co-design from the perspective of the involved partners, users, and stakeholders (in this case, the project consortium, and the vehicle operators) matters for the acceptance, adoption, and conclusive success of such a development approach. As such, the project can be seen as an in-depth user acceptance study on co-design in a technical research and innovation project and its findings will be used to assess whether and how co-design can be applied successfully in this domain. Furthermore, co-design will be revisited from a Positive User Experience perspective. This includes research on the operators' perception of their own psychological needs in the co-design process as well as methods and means for them to recognize and express their needs in the co-design process. This is essential to ensure that the operators can make meaningful contributions and that the concepts and artifacts developed in the co-design process in fact meet the operators' needs.

2.5 Privacy-based Research in Mixed Reality

2.5.1 Privacy Concerns in Mixed Reality

Multiple studies have shown, that certain aspects of XR can pose significant risks for user's privacy, security and ethical use.[40][45][23][42][46]. The first group of questions related to the problem of user identification in XR applications. The applications gather a significant amount of users' behavioural data (often - without the user's explicit content), and the pattern of these data leads to the possibility of identifying the exact user [47][39]. In addition, as many XR applications are tangled to other databases (like users' profiles on Meta), that makes it possible not just to identify the user by its behaviour and biometrics but also link this identified profile to other data provided by the user, as his name, profile photo or geography, creating the possibility for using this rich profile for multiple purposes [39][44]. In addition, the use of XR in social applications can lead to the risk of pushing users to overshare/disclose more personal information, similarly as it happened in non-XR social media domains [23]. In summarising the key privacy and security issues in XR, Khamis and Alt pointed to unintentional disclosure of confidential data, the complexity of obtaining informed consent, and emerging vulnerabilities for attacks [42]. The central ethical problem connected to that group of concerns can be described as surveillance of users from the company's side and data brokering to third parties such as insurance companies. In this context, the rich behavioural information gathered from XR

interactions can be used against the user's interests. For example, the micromovements of the person can be analysed from the health perspective and, therefore, lead to a conclusion about general health, which can affect insurance costs. In these types of situations, the XR-based data collection can lead to discriminatory actions towards users [48]. On the technological level, most of the studies focus on eye-tracking technology [4][49], which has been on the market for many years and has a clear data-gathering path. The issue identified in this domain is that technologies like eye-tracking in mixed reality, while enhancing virtual object placement, risk exposing sensitive user information, such as preferences and mental load, often without explicit consent [49]. There is a work dedicated to the problem of privacy in wearable sensors [46].

On the user side, works are dedicated to the lack of user awareness regarding data collection, opaque practices by XR developers, and potential manipulative tactics by malicious agents, exploiting these issues and XR's unique characteristics [2][3][24][25]. Despite some studies suggesting limited user concerns over data privacy in XR, others showed that users are quite concerned about it [3]. Hadan et al. identified factors that influenced users' concerns about data privacy in XR. The system, which collects cognitive, emotional, and personality data, is perceived as "too intrusive." The study also indicated an increase in users' discomfort if the XR device operated "in the background." as somehow hidden from users' attention focus. The perception of algorithmic unfairness in data collection also contributed to the level of users' discomfort [24]. The study of O'Hagan et al. showed users low awareness but high concern about AR headset activities, particularly those related to bystanders' data [50].

2.5.2 Frameworks for Privacy in Mixed Reality

There are several frameworks or foundational papers which can be considered as frameworks/guidelines in the design of XR solutions with a privacy/ethics focus. The framework and software implementation proposed by Reilly et al. aimed to synchronize privacy-related actions across both physical and virtual spaces [51]. The main features of the tool they designed include a shared ontology for physical-virtual interaction, a flexible communication model, and interface mechanisms that support user experience across realities [51]. De Guzman et al. [52] summarised a list of security and privacy concerns and created an ontology included privacy model attributes, such as integrity, non-repudiation, availability, authorization, and authentication. In addition, in their work they divide the areas which should be defended as data input, data itself, data output, user interaction, and device protection.

The XRSI Privacy Framework by the XR Safety Initiative focuses on assessing privacy risks, informing users about these risks, managing privacy, and preventing privacy-related incidents in XR settings (*XR Safety Initiative. 2020. The XRSI privacy framework*). The XRSI framework aligns its measures with major legal privacy and compliance standards. IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality [53] identifies key privacy challenges produced by Extended Reality: capturing the sensitive and behavioural data (which leads to the possible penetration of mental privacy), the adversarial effects on bystanders' privacy, total surveillance and effect on the perception of reality and propose a list of recommendations for developers in the form of suggestions from design and legislation perspective [53]. Norval et al. discussed how XR systems are linked to their environment and user actions [54]. The physical nature of XR (interactions in the real world) means that problems can lead to immediate and serious consequences, such as injury and property damage, which go beyond the usual data-related issues. Because of the severity of potential outcomes, it is important that the auditors can reconstruct or comprehend the system's behaviour and its context during operation. Addressing these points, Norval et al. developed and tested a framework with experts to assist in the development of the XR system, which aims to facilitate the capture and management of data, a necessary requirement for conducting audits [54]. Abraham et al. [55] explored the concept of fine-granular permission control for applications in XR. They found that such an approach helps users better understand the balance between system performance and data collection, allowing them to make informed decisions about their privacy [55].

The E3XR framework, developed by Lee and Hu-Au [56] evaluates XR technologies across three dimensions: ethics, educational efficacy, and eudaimonia (human flourishing). Ethics is defined as user privacy, autonomy, and avoiding harm. Education is described as immersive interactive experiences that enhance learning.

Eudaimonia assesses XR's capacity to promote personal growth and social good, as well as inclusivity and empowerment.

2.5.3 Progress beyond State of the Art

While there are several classifications of the possible risks in the XR domain, to the best of our knowledge, there is no specific classification and actionable framework to assess the particular case of XR use in the setting of off-highway machinery. The specific of working context and work requirements can produce some additional risks for data privacy and possibly create situations of conflict between data sharing prevention and working performance. Using the existent frameworks dedicated to XR privacy in combination with privacy-compliant design recommendations of GDPR and privacy engineering frameworks (Linddun), we are planning to provide the specification of the privacy risks provided by the use cases and develop privacy-related recommendations, which can be used in a broader area of augmented workplace situations.

ID:	1.1.1
Title:	start-up system
Description:	The purpose of this action is to set the system in active and functional mode.
Primary Actor:	Operator
Preconditions:	required rights/ permissions are in place
Postconditions:	system active and functional
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed that all systems are active
Frequency of use:	Every time an operation starts
Justification:	Enabling the system required to start operation

ID:	1.1.2
Title:	positioning and tracking of vehicle
Description:	Positioning and tracking of vehicle
Primary Actor:	System with potential technology: GNSS + RTK, Optical positioning system, IMU, vehicle operation data
Preconditions:	System installed and active
Postconditions:	Current position of the vehicle detected and time base logged.
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	The vehicle position and its path can be monitored by existing GNSS sensor equipment and existing surface models.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Positioning and tracking of vehicle are required for delta comparison to target surface.

ID:	1.1.3
Title:	Target surface defined
Description:	Creation of digital terrain model representing the target surface
Primary Actor:	Surface creator
Preconditions:	Surface requirements defined; access rights available
Postconditions:	Target surface created and uploaded to machine
Triggers:	Creation or modification of target surface based on initial setup, local changes of real surface or adaption based on season or snow condition, or special projects
Main Success Scenarios:	Target surface visible in the machine
Frequency of use:	On demand
Justification:	Target surface required for delta comparison to actual position

ID:	1.1.4
Title:	enter area with target surface
Description:	The purpose of this action is to move the vehicle inside a target surface mapped terrain and to enable the full functionalities. XR solutions to be developed will support the operator by providing guidance in the form of visually accessible information (e.g., laser projections in the front of the vehicle).
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	area with target surface defined all systems are active and functional
Postconditions:	delta between actual and target surface are shown to the operator

Triggers:	Grooming task
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed via XR-based HMI that he entered in area with target surface
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Task is only possible to fulfil in areas with defined target surface

ID:	1.1.5
Title:	Analysis from delta to target surface
Description:	Through comparing target and actual positioning data the delta is provided
Primary Actor:	Snow measurement system
Preconditions:	Target surface defined; actual data collected
Postconditions:	Deviation between target and actual surface calculated
Triggers:	Changing position
Main Success Scenarios:	Deviation between target and actual surface available via XR HMI
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Delta required to plan next execution tasks

ID:	1.1.6
Title:	execution to reach target
Description:	The purpose of this action is to minimize the deviation between actual and target surface.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	target surface defined, systems active, entered in area with target surface
Postconditions:	actual surface matches target surface
Triggers:	Recursive sequence of actions to minimize the deviation between actual and target surface
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed via XR HMI that actual surface matches target surface.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Action required to minimize delta from actual to target surface

ID:	1.1.7
Title:	Record result (new actual surface)
Description:	Result is recorded to know actual surface data
Primary Actor:	Snow measurement system
Preconditions:	Actual data collected
Postconditions:	Latest multiple points recorded to have a surface
Triggers:	Changing position
Main Success Scenarios:	Surface available out of the latest recorded multiple points
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Result surface data as base for next execution

ID:	1.1.8
Title:	Share new actual surface with other vehicles and to cloud
Description:	Share new actual surface with other vehicles and to cloud
Primary Actor:	Snow measurement system
Preconditions:	Actual data collected
Postconditions:	Actual surface data merged between all vehicles and shared with cloud and other vehicles
Triggers:	Changing position, end of shift, leaving area with target surface
Main Success Scenarios:	All vehicles and cloud have the actual surface data. Operator in the vehicles has access to the information via XR HMI.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Actual surface data of all vehicles as base for next execution

ID:	1.1.9
Title:	exit area
Description:	Leaving area with defined target surface
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	system active
Postconditions:	leaving area with target surface
Triggers:	Grooming task fulfilled, end of shift, task changed,
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed via XR HMI that he leaves area with defined target surface
Frequency of use:	during operation
Justification:	Either the job is done, or it must be continued on another time or by another vehicle

3.1.1.2 Obstacle Avoidance

Figure 10: Use Case 1.2 Diagram – Obstacles Detection

ID:	1.2.1
Title:	start-up system
Description:	The purpose of this action is to set the system in active and functional mode.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	required rights/ permissions are in place
Postconditions:	system active and functional
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed that all systems are active
Frequency of use:	every operation start
Justification:	Enabling the system required to start operation

ID:	1.2.2
Title:	positioning and tracking of vehicle
Description:	Positioning and tracking of vehicle
Primary Actor:	System with potential technology: GNSS + RTK, Optical positioning system, IMU, vehicle operation data
Preconditions:	System installed and active
Postconditions:	Current position of the vehicle detected and time base logged.
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	I can monitor the vehicle position and its path.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	The position is required to calculate distance to obstacles

ID:	1.2.3
Title:	Active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual surrounding information
Description:	The purpose of this action is to get/share available information acquired by a vehicle with all other entities.
Primary Actor:	Connectivity solution
Preconditions:	Surrounding information available, cloud service in place and operative, network coverage operative, system installed and active
Postconditions:	Information between cloud and vehicles aligned
Triggers:	Changing position
Main Success Scenarios:	Every vehicle has real time information
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	All available information shared with all other entities

ID:	1.2.4
Title:	Actual (static) surrounding information available
Description:	The purpose of this action is to have always the latest actual static surrounding information available in the vehicle
Primary Actor:	Surface creator
Preconditions:	3d model of the ski resort available, static obstacle information available
Postconditions:	All information gathered into digital model
Triggers:	Receive information of surrounding information
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator has access to real time static surrounding information via XR HMI
Frequency of use:	Each operation start
Justification:	Information is required to calculate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.2.5
Title:	Dynamic surrounding available
Description:	Detection system provide information about dynamic surrounding. XR solutions to be developed will support the operator by providing additional information beyond visually accessible data (e.g., panoramic thermal vision).
Primary Actor:	Object detection system
Preconditions:	Object detection system is active and functional
Postconditions:	Dynamic surrounding information available and shared
Triggers:	Object enters detection area
Main Success Scenarios:	Actual dynamic surrounding information available for all vehicles and cloud. Operator has access to the information via XR HMI
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information is required to calculate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.2.6
Title:	Check surrounding
Description:	The purpose of this action is to consolidate the human sensing and system scanning information to have a consolidated representation of the surrounding. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images).
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	Clear field of view, dead spots are covered with surrounding detection systems
Postconditions:	Operator observed/checked the consolidated representation of surrounding
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator has a clear picture on the surrounding and the obstacle around the vehicle
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information is required to evaluate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.2.7
Title:	Inform /warn operator about surrounding including real time obstacle in case of obstacle or boundary proximity
Description:	The purpose of this action is to inform the operator on obstacle or boundary proximity in time. XR solutions to be developed will implement rudimentary algorithmic means to identify abnormalities in visually non-perceivable sensor data (e.g., thermal anomalies in panoramic imagery). Active highlighting will be provided correlating detected anomalies with active light beam control to geo-reference those within the coordinate space of the operator and make them visually noticeable.
Primary Actor:	XR HMI
Preconditions:	Information exchange with other vehicles and cloud, dynamic surrounding information available, 3d model of the ski resort available, static obstacle information available, obstacle detection system,
Postconditions:	Inform in real time to avoid potential collisions
Triggers:	Obstacle or boundary within critical distance
Main Success Scenarios:	As soon as information are available via XR HMI, there is still time to react for the operator
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information mandatory for operator to set correct action

ID:	1.2.8
Title:	Execute action to avoid collision
Description:	The purpose of this action is to operate the snowgroomer avoiding potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	consolidated representation of surrounding
Postconditions:	Operator sets the next action considering available information
Triggers:	Obstacle or boundary within critical distance and this information provided to operator
Main Success Scenarios:	Set actions avoided a collision/ going off
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Without action it leads most probably to a collision

3.1.1.3 Zero Sight Navigation

Figure 11: Use Case 1.3 Diagram – Zero sight navigation

ID:	1.3.1
Title:	start-up system
Description:	The purpose of this action is to set the system in active and functional mode.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	required rights/ permissions are in place
Postconditions:	system active and functional
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is informed that all systems are active
Frequency of use:	every operation start
Justification:	Enabling the system required to start operation

ID:	1.3.2
Title:	positioning and tracking of vehicle
Description:	Positioning and tracking of vehicle
Primary Actor:	System with potential technology: GNSS + RTK, Optical positioning system, IMU, vehicle operation data
Preconditions:	System installed and active
Postconditions:	Current position of the vehicle detected and time base logged.
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	The vehicle position and its path can be monitored.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Positioning and tracking of vehicle are required for delta comparison to target surface. The position is required to calculate distance to obstacles

ID:	1.3.3
Title:	Active connection to cloud or other vehicles to get/share actual surrounding information
Description:	The purpose of this action is to get/share available information acquired by a vehicle with all other entities.
Primary Actor:	Connectivity solution
Preconditions:	Surrounding information available, cloud service in place and operative, network coverage operative, system installed and active
Postconditions:	Information between cloud and vehicles aligned
Triggers:	Changing position
Main Success Scenarios:	Every vehicle has real time information
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	All available information shared with all other entities

ID:	1.3.4
Title:	Actual (static) surrounding information available
Description:	The purpose of this action is to have always the latest actual static surrounding information available in the vehicle
Primary Actor:	Surface creator
Preconditions:	3d model of the ski resort available, static obstacle information available
Postconditions:	All information gathered into digital model
Triggers:	Receive information of surrounding information
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator has access to real time static surrounding information via XR HMI
Frequency of use:	Each operation start
Justification:	Information is required to calculate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.3.5
Title:	Dynamic surrounding available
Description:	Detection system provide information about dynamic surrounding.
Primary Actor:	Object detection system
Preconditions:	Object detection system is active and functional
Postconditions:	Dynamic surrounding information available and shared
Triggers:	Object enters detection area
Main Success Scenarios:	Actual dynamic surrounding information available for all vehicles and cloud. Operator has access to the information via XR HMI
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information is required to calculate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.3.6
Title:	Enter area with zero sight. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment).
Description:	Entering in area with zero sight
Primary Actor:	Operator
Preconditions:	Environmental conditions, system active and functional
Postconditions:	Entering in area with zero sight
Triggers:	Grooming task requires entering in area with zero sight
Main Success Scenarios:	No more orientation for the operator feasible
Frequency of use:	depending on environmental conditions
Justification:	This is the starting point of this scenario

ID:	1.3.7
Title:	Check surrounding
Description:	The purpose of this action is to consolidate the human sensing and system scanning information to have a consolidated representation of surrounding
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	All systems active and functional to provide to the operator clear view information
Postconditions:	Operator observed/checked the consolidated representation of surrounding
Triggers:	Push start button inside snow groomer
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator has a clear picture on the surrounding and the obstacle around the vehicle via XR HMI.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information is required to evaluate the distance to obstacles

ID:	1.3.8
Title:	Inform /warn operator about surrounding. XR solutions to be developed will implement rudimentary algorithmic means to identify abnormalities in visually non-perceivable sensor data (e.g., thermal anomalies in panoramic imagery).
Description:	The purpose of this action is to inform in real time the operator on obstacle or boundary proximity in time.
Primary Actor:	XR HMI
Preconditions:	Information exchange with other vehicles and cloud, dynamic surrounding information available, 3d model of the ski resort available, static obstacle information available, obstacle detection system,
Postconditions:	Inform in real time to avoid potential collisions
Triggers:	Obstacle or boundary within critical distance
Main Success Scenarios:	As soon as information are available via XR HMI, there is still time to react for the operator
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Information mandatory for operator to set correct action

ID:	1.3.9
Title:	Inform about proposed actions (XR technology)
Description:	The purpose of this action is to inform in real time the operator on obstacle or boundary proximity in time.
Primary Actor:	XR HMI
Preconditions:	Information exchange with other vehicles and cloud, dynamic surrounding information available, 3d model of the ski resort available, static obstacle information available, obstacle detection system,
Postconditions:	Action proposed to operator
Triggers:	obstacle or boundary proximity
Main Success Scenarios:	Operator is aware about proposed action via XR HMI, there is still time to react for the operator.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Operation requires a proposed action, as he has no direct view to the surrounding

ID:	1.3.10
Title:	Execute action to avoid collision
Description:	The purpose of this action is to operate the snowgroomer avoiding potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Operator/Snowgroomer system
Preconditions:	consolidated representation of surrounding, proposed corrective action information available
Postconditions:	Operator/ Snowgroomer system sets the next action considering available information
Triggers:	Operator: The operator moves the snowgroomer to avoid the collision. Snowgroomer System: Operator is not acting in time or in a proper matter, so the Snowgroomer System acts as final escalation level
Main Success Scenarios:	Set actions to avoid a collision.
Frequency of use:	Continuously during operation
Justification:	Without action it leads most probably to a collision

3.1.2 Logistics Use Case

These use cases focus container handling with a machine called reachstacker. Latest generations of these machines can be controlled remotely with the operator doesn't have direct visibility to the controlled machine. Remote operations can improve overall operator performance primarily by extending visibility with multiple camera views. Cameras can be zoomed in on the container and big angles all around the machine can be seen. It helps operators to do the work more efficiently as well as enhance safety.

Remote operations also serve to improve the working environment for equipment operators by physically removing them from the machines into the safety and comfort of a control room. The control room also enables a more versatile workplace. If some tasks could be automated, one operator can even operate many machines efficiently from one desk.

3.1.2.1 Remote Controller RS: Job order to pick from the stack

Figure 12: Use-Case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.1 – Pick container from stack”

ID:	2.1.1
Title:	Container pick job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk’s PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	Job order received from TOS
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn’t know which container to handle.

ID:	2.1.2
Title:	Move spreader on top of target slot
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the position (column and row in selected block) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPS) over target slot and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	Job has been received accordingly and container has been selected.
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The spreader must be positioned perfectly above the container, otherwise it will not be able to grasp the container accordingly.

ID:	2.1.3
Title:	Select container size
Description:	The operator selected the container size according to the TOS job order so the spreader will be set to the right width. This information is needed, so that the container can be grasped accordingly
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The correct size of the container is selected
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned above the selected container and the request for the container size has been performed.
Main Success Scenarios:	The right size of the container has been selected, so the spreader can be set.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The right size of the container needs to be selected, otherwise the reachstacker could damage the container

ID:	2.1.4
Title:	Position spreader to twistlocks
Description:	The spreaders will be positioned accordingly to the container size and the edges of the container, so that it can be picked up appropriately. A XR system will inform the human operator (visually) that the spreader is in the right position or how the spreader needs to be positioned.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned above the container and the right container size has been selected.
Postconditions:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the container
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned over the container and the container size has been selected.
Main Success Scenarios:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the selected container.
Frequency of use:	Frequently.
Justification:	The spreader needs to be positioned precisely for picking up the specific container and to ensure that the container can be grasped safely.

ID:	2.1.5
Title:	Stop machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Difficult to put a number on it.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.1.6
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic, and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.1.7
Title:	Twistlocks locked
Description:	Remote operator lowers the spreader so that twistlocks goes into corner pockets. Twistlocks are locked automatically when landpin information in all corners is OK. RC desk send job completed information to TOS.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned perfectly above the container
Postconditions:	A twistlocks are in place at the container and are locked securely. The remote operator is informed by the XR system
Triggers:	Activation by the remote operator
Main Success Scenarios:	The twistlocks are in the correct position and are locked, activated by the remote operator. The operator receives the confirmation through the XR system.
Frequency of use:	Frequently.
Justification:	The twistlocks need to be locked, otherwise the container cannot be lifted in a safe way.

ID:	2.1.8
Title:	Lift container to safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator must lift the container to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the container is in a safe height position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped in a secure way.
Postconditions:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the twistlocks are in place.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The container needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding the container against anything else.

3.1.2.2 Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the stack

Figure 13: Use-Case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.2 – Place container to stack”

ID:	2.2.1
Title:	Container place job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk’s PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered by the job order sent from the Terminal Operating System (TOS).
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn’t know which container to handle.

ID:	2.2.2
Title:	Move spreader to correct position in stack
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the position (column and row in selected block) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPI) over target slot and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered as soon as the task is started to position the container in the stack.
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The spreader must be positioned perfectly above the container, otherwise it will not be able to position the container accordingly.

ID:	2.2.3
Title:	Position container in relation to container underneath and adjacent containers
Description:	Remote operator lowers the container so that container corners are aligned with the container below. Corner castings must be on top of each other because it is carrying the load. Twistlocks can be opened if the container is in correct position. and landpin information in all corners is OK. The operator lifts spreader above safe height. RC desk send job completed information to TOS.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system. The spreader is on top of correct position above safe height.
Postconditions:	The container is placed without collisions and is in correct position. Job complete information is sent to TOS.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered as soon as the container is positioned above the stack. The remote operator starts positioning the container in relation to the containers below.
Main Success Scenarios:	Container is placed in correct position without collisions and information sent to TOS.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This task will actually position the container at the correct position.

ID:	2.2.4
Title:	Stop Machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Depends on different environmental and work factors.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.2.5
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic, and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.2.6
Title:	Release spreader
Description:	The container must be released from the spreader. The twistlocks will be released and the container will remain at its position. The XR system will inform the remote operator that the container has been released and the spreader has reached its correct position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been placed correctly.
Postconditions:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Triggers:	Correct positioning of the container.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	This activity is important for a safe release and correct positioning of the container.

ID:	2.2.7
Title:	Lift container to safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator must lift the container to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the container is in a safe height position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped in a secure way.
Postconditions:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the twistlocks are in place.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The container needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding the container against anything else.

3.1.2.3 Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the ground

Figure 14: Use-Case Diagram for "Logistics Use Case 2.3 – Pick container from ground"

ID:	2.3.1
Title:	Container pick job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk's PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	Job order received from TOS
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn't know which container to handle.

ID:	2.3.2
Title:	Move spreader on top of target slot
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the position (column and row in selected block) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPI) over target slot and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	Job order received from TOS and that remote operator has started moving the reachstacker
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The spreader needs to be positioned on top of the selected container, otherwise it cannot define the width of the spreader for picking it up.

ID:	2.3.3
Title:	Select container size
Description:	The operator selected the container size according to the TOS job order so the spreader will be set to the right width. This information is needed, so that the container can be grasped accordingly
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The correct size of the container is selected
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned above the selected container and the request for the container size has been performed.
Main Success Scenarios:	The right size of the container has been selected, so the spreader can be set.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The right size of the container needs to be selected, otherwise the reachstacker could damage the container

ID:	2.3.4
Title:	Position spreader to twistlocks
Description:	The spreaders will be positioned accordingly to the container size and the edges of the container, so that it can be picked up appropriately. A XR system will inform the human operator (visually) that the spreader is in the right position or how the spreader needs to be positioned.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned above the container and the right container size has been selected.
Postconditions:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the container
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned over the container and the container size has been selected.
Main Success Scenarios:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the selected container.
Frequency of use:	Frequently.
Justification:	The spreader needs to be positioned precisely for picking up the specific container and to ensure that the container can be grasped safely.

ID:	2.3.5
Title:	Stop machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Difficult to put a number on it.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.3.6
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic, and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.3.7
Title:	Twistlocks locked
Description:	Remote operator lowers the spreader so that twistlocks goes into corner pockets. Twistlocks are locked automatically when landpin information in all corners is OK.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned perfectly above the container
Postconditions:	The twistlocks are in place at the container and are locked securely. The remote operator is informed by the XR system
Triggers:	Activation by the remote operator
Main Success Scenarios:	The twistlocks are in the correct position and are locked, activated by the remote operator. The operator receives the confirmation through the XR system.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The twistlocks need to be locked, otherwise the container cannot be lifted in a safe way.

ID:	2.3.8
Title:	Lift container to safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator has to lift the container to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the container is in a safe height position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped in a secure way.
Postconditions:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the twistlocks are in place.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The container needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding the container against anything else.

3.1.2.4 Remote controlled RS: Job order to place on the ground

Figure 15: Use-Case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.4 – Place container on ground”

ID:	2.4.1
Title:	Container place job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk's PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered by the job order sent from the Terminal Operating System (TOS).
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn't know which container to handle.

ID:	2.4.2
Title:	Move spreader on top of correct position
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the position (column and row in selected block) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPI) over target slot and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered as soon as the task is started to position the container in the stack.
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This task is required as it will make it possible to place the container exactly where it needs to be positioned.

ID:	2.4.3
Title:	Position container in relation to painted lines and adjacent containers
Description:	Remote operator lowers the container so that container corners are aligned with the painted lines on ground and adjacent containers. Container must be inside the painted slot position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped accordingly and the reachstacker is carrying the container towards the position where it needs to be placed.
Postconditions:	The container is placed without collisions and is in correct position. Job complete information is sent to TOS.
Triggers:	The container has been grasped and the position of placing it is known.
Main Success Scenarios:	Container is placed in correct position without collisions and information sent to TOS.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This activity described the position of the container on a place on the ground, which is one of the main tasks of the reachstacker.

ID:	2.4.4
Title:	Stop machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Difficult to put a number on it.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.4.5
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic, and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.4.6
Title:	Release spreader
Description:	Twistlocks can be opened if the container is in correct position. and landpin information in all corners is OK. The container must be released from the spreader. The twistlocks will be released and the container will remain at its position. The XR system will inform the remote operator that the container has been released and the spreader has reached its correct position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been placed correctly.
Postconditions:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Triggers:	Correct positioning of the container.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	This activity is important for a safe release and correct positioning of the container.

ID:	2.4.7
Title:	Lift container to safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator has to lift the container to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the container is in a safe height position. The operator lifts spreader above safe height. RC desk send job completed information to TOS.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped in a secure way.
Postconditions:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the twistlocks are in place.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The container needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding the container against anything else.

3.1.2.5 Remote controlled RS: Job order to pick from the trailer

Figure 16: Use-Case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.5 – Pick container from the trailer”

ID:	2.5.1
Title:	Container pick job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk’s PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	Job order received from TOS
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn’t know which container to handle.

ID:	2.5.2
Title:	Move spreader on top of trailer
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the selected trailer and to correct position on the trailer (front, middle or back position with 20-foot containers) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPI) over the target trailer and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A job has been assigned to the remote operator and it is clear which container needs to be picked up from which trailer.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	The assignment of a job and the start of the machine
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This activity places the spreader on top of the trailer, enabling the remote operator to finally pick up the container from the trailer.

ID:	2.5.3
Title:	Select container size
Description:	The operator selected the container size according to the TOS job order so the spreader will be set to the right width. This information is needed, so that the container can be grasped accordingly
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The correct size of the container is selected
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned above the selected container and the request for the container size has been performed.
Main Success Scenarios:	The right size of the container has been selected, so the spreader can be set.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	The right size of the container needs to be selected, otherwise the reachstacker could damage the container

ID:	2.5.4
Title:	Position spreader to twistlock corners
Description:	The spreaders will be positioned accordingly to the container size and the edges of the container, so that it can be picked up appropriately. A XR system will inform the human operator (visually) that the spreader is in the right position or how the spreader needs to be positioned.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned above the container and the right container size has been selected.
Postconditions:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the container
Triggers:	The spreader is positioned over the container and the container size has been selected.
Main Success Scenarios:	The spreader is positioned precisely for picking up the selected container.
Frequency of use:	Frequently.
Justification:	The spreader needs to be positioned precisely for picking up the specific container and to ensure that the container can be grasped safely.

ID:	2.5.5
Title:	Stop machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Difficult to put a number on it.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.5.6
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic, and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.5.7
Title:	Twistlocks locked
Description:	Remote operator lowers the spreader so that twistlocks goes into corner pockets. Twistlocks are locked automatically when landpin information in all corners is OK.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The spreader is positioned perfectly above the container
Postconditions:	The twistlocks are in place at the container and are locked securely. The remote operator is informed by the XR system
Triggers:	Activation by the remote operator
Main Success Scenarios:	The twistlocks are in the correct position and are locked, activated by the remote operator. The operator receives the confirmation through the XR system.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The twistlocks need to be locked, otherwise the container cannot be lifted in a safe way.

ID:	2.5.8
Title:	Lift container to safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator must lift the container to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the container is in a safe height position. The operator lifts spreader above safe height. RC desk send job completed information to TOS.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been grasped in a secure way.
Postconditions:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the twistlocks are in place.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The container needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding the container against anything else.

3.1.2.6 Remote controlled RS: Job order to place to the trailer

Figure 17: Use-Case Diagram for “Logistics Use Case 2.6 – Place container to the trailer”

ID:	2.6.1
Title:	Container place job
Description:	Job orders are sent from Terminal Operating System (TOS) to the free remote control desk’s PC. User selects job with the user interface and RC desk will be connected to the right machine safely (video screens are turned on and controls are connected to the selected machine).
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	TOS has sent the job order to the remote-control desk and it can be executed. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The job is selected and ready to be executed.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered by the job order sent from the Terminal Operating System (TOS).
Main Success Scenarios:	Job order received correctly to RC desk PC and operator has selected the job.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This is the start activity for the overall task at hand. Without the assigned job the remote operator doesn’t know which container to handle.

ID:	2.6.2
Title:	Move spreader on top of trailer
Description:	Remote operator moves RS next to the selected trailer and to correct position on the trailer (front, middle or back position with 20-foot containers) appointed by job order. Operator moves spreader with the help of Container Positioning System (CPS) over the target trailer and changes spreader size according to TOS job order. XR solutions to be developed will provide the operator with a visualization methodology for non-visually accessible data (e.g., false-colour coded thermographic images of the environment) to prevent accidental obstacle collision.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Job is selected. No alarms or warnings are not active, and machine is working normally. Machine is in remote control mode. Infrastructure safety system is not activated (gates are closed etc.). Remote control desk is operating normally, and operator is logged in the system.
Postconditions:	The spreader is in correct position (± 200 mm from nominal position horizontally and above safe position) on top of the target container.
Triggers:	This activity is triggered as soon as the task is started to position the container on the trailer
Main Success Scenarios:	Machine and spreader move to correct position fast.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This task is required as it will make it possible to place the container exactly where it needs to be positioned, namely on the trailer.

ID:	2.6.3
Title:	Position container on twistlocks (or guides) on trailer
Description:	Remote operator lowers the container so that container corners are aligned with the twistlocks (or guides) on the targeted trailer. The position must be very accurate, otherwise the container cannot be fixed accordingly.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container is lifted by the reachstacker, and the remote operator knows on which trailer the container needs to be placed.
Postconditions:	The container is perfectly aligned with the twistlocks on the trailer.
Triggers:	The remote operator receives the job and knows which trailer needs to be loaded.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container is perfectly aligned with the twistlocks on the trailer.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	This activity is needed to align the container with the trailer, so it can be safely mounted on the targeted trailer. Without perfect alignment, the twistlocks won't close and the container will not be securely fixed.

ID:	2.6.4
Title:	Stop machine
Description:	The machine needs to stop immediately if a person enters the surrounding of the vehicle or if a potential collision can occur with the container being carried. The human operator will be informed by the XR system, e.g., visualization, acoustic or haptic feedback informing the remote operator that a dangerous situation has appeared.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	A dangerous situation has been identified, e.g., a person in the vicinity of the reachstacker or an imminent collision with the container.
Postconditions:	The machine has come to a full stop
Triggers:	The identification of a dangerous situation.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reachstacker has come to a complete stop and a collision has been avoided.
Frequency of use:	Every time a dangerous situation occurs. Difficult to put a number on it.
Justification:	The system needs to avoid dangerous situations, to avoid (deadly) accidents to humans or damage to machines.

ID:	2.6.5
Title:	Check surroundings
Description:	A sensor system will continuously check the surrounding of the reachstacker if no obstacle is near or if the container will not collide with anything in the surroundings and will inform the remote operator with XR technologies (i.e., visual, haptic and acoustic) about potential collisions.
Primary Actor:	Sensor system on the reachstacker
Preconditions:	The sensor system is up and running
Postconditions:	If a potential collision is imminent, the XR technologies inform the human operator in an intuitive way, so that the operator can also still focus on the task at hand
Triggers:	The surroundings are constantly checked, so this task is activated as soon as the machine is started,
Main Success Scenarios:	The surroundings are checked constantly, and dangerous situations are identified early enough
Frequency of use:	Continuously
Justification:	To avoid dangerous situation and collisions which could endanger other people or damage the cargo, continuous checking of the surroundings is a must.

ID:	2.6.6
Title:	Release spreader
Description:	Twistlocks can be opened if the container is in correct position. and landpin information in all corners is OK. The container must be released from the spreader. The twistlocks will be released and the container will remain at its position at the trailer. The XR system will inform the remote operator that the container has been released and the spreader has reached its correct position.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	The container has been placed correctly.
Postconditions:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Triggers:	Correct positioning of the container.
Main Success Scenarios:	The container is safely released, and the spreader is correctly released.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	This activity is important for a safe release and correct positioning of the container.

ID:	2.6.7
Title:	Lift spreader over safe height
Description:	After the twistlocks are secured in place, the remote operator has to lift the spreader to a secure height, so that collision can be avoided and the reachstacker can be moved in a safe way. The remote operator gets informed by the XR technologies that the spreader is in a safe height position. The operator lifts spreader above safe height. RC desk send job completed information to TOS.
Primary Actor:	Remote operator
Preconditions:	Twistlocks are in secure place, and nothing is attached to the spreader
Postconditions:	The spreader is lifted to a secure heights
Triggers:	Remote operator performs the lifting task, after the container has been secured on the trailer.
Main Success Scenarios:	The spreader has been lifted without collision and is in a height that no other collisions will occur.
Frequency of use:	Frequently
Justification:	The spreader needs to be lifted in a safe way and be at a safe height, so that the remote operator can drive the reachstacker around without colliding against anything else.

3.1.3 Construction Use Case

In the following section, the actions of the three use cases which will make use of XR-technology are described in more detail.

3.1.3.1 Finish Grading

Figure 18: Use Case 3.1 Diagram – Finish Grading

ID:	3.1.1
Title:	Check general system status
Description:	The operator must start the onboard system and the engine and assess the provided status information about the machine and the 3D-control system as well as the XR-system. Colour coded ambient light are used to indicate operability. detailed information about the operability.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The machines onboard system is operational and can display the function indicators.
Postconditions:	All necessary system functions are highlighted as operational.
Triggers:	Starting the machine.
Main Success Scenarios:	All necessary system functions are highlighted as operational.
Frequency of use:	After each start-up.
Justification:	Having an overview of all system components and their operational readiness is crucial for any kind of work.

ID:	3.1.2
Title:	Set reference height.
Description:	The operator navigates to the 3D-control system UI and choose “set reference height”. After setting up the desired model, the display shows a virtual 3D machine model and environment mode with the desired height in relation to the virtual 3D-map of the surrounding.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The 3D-control system is operational. A reference object is in reach.
Postconditions:	The operator can choose a referencing method.
Triggers:	Set reference height manually. (Alternative: use predefined model)
Main Success Scenarios:	The “dialogue” to choose the method of setting the reference height opens. The operator chooses the desired method.
Frequency of use:	Regularly (during 3D-control setup)
Justification:	Setting up a proper target design is fundamental for proper working results. A good alignment between virtual models and real environment is necessary.

ID:	3.1.3
Title:	Set reference height manually.
Description:	The operator defines a reference height on a static object e.g., a boarder stone or a kerbstone. By moving the excavator’s bucket to the object, a reference height is taught to the system. The target point is immediately displayed in the VR-model of the environment.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator activates the manual teaching mode for setting the reference height in the UI.
Postconditions:	The 3D-control system is referenced to a certain point.
Triggers:	No design model is available, and a manual setup is necessary.
Main Success Scenarios:	The reference height is taught correctly. An intuitive reference to the real object is highlighted in the XR-System.
Frequency of use:	Regularly (During 3D-control setup)
Justification:	Setting the reference height manually is a common situation in small construction projects and enables the operator to work model based without an additional civil engineer which creates a model.

ID:	3.1.4
Title:	Check reference height
Description:	The operator checks the alignment and plausibility between reality and digital model from the 3D-control system. A virtual 3D environment of the machine and scanned surrounding with an intersection of the design model makes it possible to assess the proper design height. The XR mechanisms to be developed should provide more natural means to assess the quality, providing a visualization which “pretends” the excavation works to have finished already using texture mapping on planned and final surface models.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	A reference height is set in the system.
Postconditions:	The digital design model aligns to the working environment.
Triggers:	After design data setup.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator intuitively and clearly assesses the alignment between real environment and digital model.
Frequency of use:	Regularly (During 3D-control setup)
Justification:	Checking the proper design in relation to the geo-localisation and the environment of the excavator is crucial for proper working results.

ID:	3.1.5
Title:	Make level pass
Description:	The operator levels out the entire working area within reach. Piles should be flattened, and pits should be filled. The displays show a heatmap of the working area to assess the mass distribution.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	A reference height is set in the system and can be referenced to the current working area.
Postconditions:	The area within reach is flattened according to the design data.
Triggers:	After proper design setup, working starts. Making rough level pass
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator has an overview on how the material must be distributed across the working area and flattens the area as fast and as efficiently as possible.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	Provision of a good levelling is a regular task and XR can help to plan the working routine

ID:	3.1.6
Title:	Move excavator
Description:	The operator moves the excavator to reach areas which cannot be accessed in the current position. The display shows the VR environment and the radius of operation of the excavator and helps to plan the next position
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The current working area is finished.
Postconditions:	A new position to continue the work is reached.
Triggers:	The surface within in reach is levelled out.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator can assess the best place to continue operation.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	Regular change of position takes time and reduces efficiency. A VR- visualization of the surrounding helps to plan the next positioning.

ID:	3.1.7
Title:	Finish grading
Description:	The operator smooths out the surface by moving the bottom plate of the bucket across the flattened working area. The final surface is scanned, visualized on the display, and can be saved for an as-built documentation.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	A basic level is generated.
Postconditions:	A smooth and slightly compacted surface is generated according to the target design.
Triggers:	This is the final shaping procedure after levelling.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator finishes the grading within the working area as fast and as efficiently as possible. The final surface is recorded automatically as DGM.
Frequency of use:	Regularly
Justification:	A smooth surface is the prerequisite for the following surveying and construction work.

3.1.3.2 Collision Avoidance

Figure 19: Use Case 3.2 Diagram – Collision Avoidance

ID:	3.2.1
Title:	Check side and rear in CMS
Description:	The operator checks the camera screens to detect possible persons in the danger area.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator wants to perform a potentially risky movement.
Postconditions:	The operator detects if there is a person in the danger area.
Triggers:	A critical movement is planned and there is a risk of persons in the danger area.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator only checks the CMS if there is a critical situation. Otherwise, the operator can work continuously.
Frequency of use:	Very often
Justification	Excavators have poor visibility and there is always a risk of hitting a person while moving.

ID:	3.2.2
Title:	Detect obstacle
Description:	The operator detects a person in the danger area. Person detection software can detect the person before the operator and gives a visual indication. XR solutions to be developed will implement rudimentary algorithmic means to identify abnormalities in visually non-perceivable sensor data (e.g., thermal anomalies in panoramic imagery). Active highlighting will be provided correlating detected anomalies with active light beam control to geo-reference those within the coordinate space of the operator and make them visually or audibly noticeable.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator checks the CMS. A person is in the field of view of the CMS.
Postconditions:	The operator clearly sees the person in the danger area and can assess further actions.
Triggers:	A person is in the field of view of a camera.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator only checks the CMS if there is a critical situation. Otherwise, the operator can work continuously.
Frequency of use:	Very often
Justification	People are usually walking closely to a construction machine due to narrow special conditions on a construction site.

ID:	3.2.2
Title:	Oversee obstacle
Description:	The operator does not detect the person in the danger area. Distraction or annoyance are keeping the operator from looking at the videos. A person detection which indicates the risk by e.g., ambient light can help to get the attention of the operator.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator checks the CMS. A person is in the field of view of the CMS.
Postconditions:	The operator starts the desired movement and potentially hits the person.
Triggers:	The operator is distracted or annoyed and will not look at the video streams.
Main Success Scenarios:	A collision warning system increases its warning indicators.
Frequency of use:	regularly
Justification	To oversee someone walking through the danger area is a critical situation that might lead to an accident when the excavator moves.

ID:	3.2.3
Title:	Stop movement
Description:	The operator stops the movement because of a detected person in the danger area.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator detected a person, or the collision warning system indicated a potential collision and informed the operator.
Postconditions:	The operator contacts the person in the danger zone to leave the area.
Triggers:	The operator detects the person just before the movement is initialized.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator does not initiate the movement and gets in contact with the person.
Frequency of use:	Occasionally
Justification	This is the desired behaviour and the main goal of the collision warning system.

ID:	3.2.4
Title:	Deactivate CMS
Description:	The operator deactivates the CMS and the collision warning system.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator is annoyed by the system and false alarms.
Postconditions:	The operator might hit a person because the CMS is deactivated and there is no option to control the danger area.
Triggers:	The operator is annoyed by too many false positives or too annoying indication signals (usually loud beeping).
Main Success Scenarios:	This should not happen. There should be no false alarms and the collision avoidance system should not be cumbersome during operation.
Frequency of use:	Rarely
Justification	This is a common case but should be strictly avoided. With the help of an immersive XR-technology, the level of annoyance should be reduced.

3.1.3.3 Infield Design

Figure 20: Use Case 3.3 Diagram – Infield Design

ID:	3.3.1
Title:	Check system status
Description:	The operator must start the onboard system and the engine and assess the provided status information about the machine and the 3D-control system as well as the XR-system. Colour coded light helps to get a quick overview of the overall system status.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The machines onboard system is operational and can display the function indicators.
Postconditions:	All necessary system functions are highlighted as operational.
Triggers:	Before the work starts, the check-up is mandatory.
Main Success Scenarios:	All necessary system functions are highlighted as operational.
Frequency of use:	After each start-up.
Justification	This is a crucial part before starting the operation. Insufficient functionality might lead to poor performance or wrong working results.

ID:	3.3.2
Title:	Navigate GUI to infield design
Description:	The operator uses the user interface to open the infield design wizard. With support of 3D visualization, the design process is much more intuitive.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The machine control system and XR-System are operational.
Postconditions:	A dialog is opened which enables the design of a digital terrain model in an intuitive and easy way.
Triggers:	The operator needs to setup a target design by his own.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator can use the UI intuitively and easily.
Frequency of use:	Occasionally.
Justification	As more surveying knowledge and tasks are shifted to the machine operator, infield design tasks are getting more common. To help the operator with visual aids helps to guarantee good working results.

ID:	3.3.3
Title:	Check outline of the pit
Description:	The operator can set the outline as quickly as possible and with a clear reference to the real environment. Creating an outline is usually done by setting up marks in the environment and move the bucket to them to teach them in. With a complete digital design process that references real environment scans and imagery, the process can be more intuitive and safer.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator has a reference in the environment to setup the outline correctly.
Postconditions:	An outline of the DTM is generated it is clearly referenced to the environment.
Triggers:	The infield design process is started.
Main Success Scenarios:	The setup of the environment is easy and quickly and the operator feels confident to have the proper alignment to reality.
Frequency of use:	Occasionally
Justification	Digital terrain models are composed by an outline and a profile.

ID:	3.3.4
Title:	Check profile of the pit
Description:	The operator can set profile of the pit to generate a complete DTM. With the help of VR-content in the display with reference to the real environment (by using a real-time 3D-scan) the profile setup is much more intuitive than the conventional way (setting coordinates in a 2D-diagram)
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	The operator has setup an outline of the pit.
Postconditions:	The proper profile is added to the outline and a complete DTM is generated.
Triggers:	The outline of the pit has been created.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator can easily and intuitive add a profile to the outline. The complete DTM is referenced to the real environment.
Frequency of use:	Occasionally
Justification	Setting up the profile completes the DTM design process.

ID:	3.3.5
Title:	Verify Model
Description:	The operator verifies the proper design. A VR-visualization of the machine, the environment and the design model in proper alignment helps to get a clear indication of plausibility.
Primary Actor:	operator
Preconditions:	A complete DTM is created.
Postconditions:	The DTM is verified.
Triggers:	The outline and profile of the pit are designed.
Main Success Scenarios:	The operator can see the final design in alignment to the real environment and how the building will look after completion. Relevant process data as moved mass balance or total volume is calculated.
Frequency of use:	Occasionally
Justification	The final design evaluation and proper reference to the environment is relevant to avoid over- or under digging and therefore low efficiency due to unnecessary mass movement.

3.2 Functional Requirements

Following the use case scenarios described in the previous section, four main sets of functional requirements are derived. The first encompasses the technologies and methodologies generally developed in the project (General Functional Requirements) and describes those requirements that are to be expected to be fulfilled by the technologies regarding of the use case scenarios and are even applicable beyond the scope of the three use cases. The other three sets of functional requirements are specific to each use case.

All functional requirements are identified by a unique Requirement ID, so they can be traced within the scope of the deliverable, as well as throughout the development of the technologies. Use case specific functional requirements are also associated with at least one scenario as described in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** Lastly, each functional requirement is appointed a Level, based on a MUST/SHOULD/MAY rating. Functional requirements marked as “MUST” are crucial and obligatory to be implemented. Those marked as “SHOULD” described functionalities that are considered welcome features and the ones marked as “MAY” are optional ones.

It should be noted that the Functional Requirements described in this section, list the user-level requirements. As such, they describe visible functionalities that the THEIA^{XR} technologies must, should or may provide. Functional requirements that describe functionalities and organizations that are internal to the functioning of the system will not be covered in this section. These functionalities, named Technical Functionalities, will be described in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**

3.2.1 General Functional Requirements

The general functional requirements of THEIA^{XR} are provided in Table 1.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Status
GFR1	The developed and deployed THEIA ^{XR} technologies must clearly indicate if it is fully operational or not (e.g., due to missing sensor signals)	MUST	
GFR2	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system should be integrated into the mobile machinery	SHOULD	
GFR3	While the human operator performs the task with the machinery, the sensors must continue scanning the environment for identifying dangerous situations	MUST	

GFR4	The operator support system must have XR based UI for better situation awareness	MUST	
GFR5	The operator support system must have multimodal UI elements (e.g., visual and haptic feedback)	MUST	Updated
GFR6	The operator support system should allow user to customise UI components	SHOULD	
GFR7	The operator must be able to overcome the guidance provided by the support system, as he/she is the ultimate decision-maker.	MUST	
GFR8	A software development toolkit must be available for developing UIs and hosting XR applications on the visualization infrastructure and interaction systems	SHOULD	Updated
GFR9	The XR-based system must not distract the operator or hinder the operator's perception.	MUST	

Table 1: General Functional Requirements of THEIA^{XR}

Justification for updates:

- GFR5: Removed sound as a feedback channel, as this is not feasible in the actual working environment.
- GFR8: Changed to SHOULD as this is not realisable across all use cases and would not contribute significantly to the scope of the project.

3.2.2 Snow Grooming Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements

The functional requirements associated with the snow grooming use case are presented in Table 2.

Requirements ID	Description	Level	Status
FR.UC1.001	XR HMI system must show the distance between actual and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	
FR.UC1.002	XR HMI system must show the distance between blade and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	
FR.UC1.003	XR HMI system must show the distance between tracks and target-height in an intuitive way.	MUST	
FR.UC1.004	XR HMI system should indicate the required action to minimize delta to target surface	SHOULD	
FR.UC1.005	XR HMI system should inform operator on fulfilment rate	SHOULD	
FR.UC1.006	XR HMI system must inform operator in case of obstacle or boundary proximity.	MUST	
FR.UC1.007	XR HMI system must inform operator in case of new static or dynamic obstacle information availability	MUST	
FR.UC1.008	XR HMI system must inform operator about location and identification of obstacle	MUST	
FR.UC1.009	XR HMI system must inform operator about proposed action to avoid collision with an obstacle	MUST	

Table 2: Snow Grooming Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements XR

3.2.3 Logistics Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements

The functional requirements associated with the snow grooming use case are presented in Table 3.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Status
FR.UC2.001	The teleoperation support system should show to the operator the job order via AR/XR in video feed. E.g., also highlights container location	SHOULD	
FR.UC2.002	The teleoperation support system must show to operator spreader corner in video overlay via AR/XR	MUST	
FR.UC2.003	The teleoperation support system should show to operator distance between handled objects (e.g., spreader and container) in video overlay via AR/XR	SHOULD	
FR.UC2.004	The teleoperation support system must allow to operator to choose XR supported 3D and/or bird view to lift/lay down container without collision	MUST	
FR.UC2.005	The teleoperation support system should provide to operator XR-supported safety warning, if someone (human or machine is arriving close to working area	SHOULD	
FR.UC2.006	The teleoperation support system must provide haptic feedback to operator	MUST	
FR.UC2.007	The teleoperation support system must provide audio feedback to operator from distance and location before collision	MUST	

Table 3: Logistics Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements

3.2.4 Construction Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements

The functional requirements associated with the construction use case are presented in Table 4.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Status
FR.UC3.001	The operator interface system must visualize a digital representation of the machine and a terrain model of the environment.	MUST	
FR.UC3.002	The operator interface system must visualize the excavator's bucket position in relation to the target design height at that particular position	MUST	
FR.UC3.004	The operator interface system must visualize the point cloud data from the LIDaR as a continuously updated map.	MUST	
FR.UC2.005	The operator interface system must inform the operator about persons in the slewing radius in an intuitive but unobtrusive way.	MUST	
FR.UC3.006	The operator interface system should augment video streams with digital design data.	SHOULD	
FR.UC3.007	The operator interface system should visualize the overall working area and the delta between actual and target height across the whole map.	SHOULD	
FR.UC3.008	The operator interface system should show the position of known underground media in an intuitive way.	SHOULD	
FR.UC3.009	The operator interface system should enable the operator to modify the digital design model within the augmented video feed.	SHOULD	

Table 4: Construction Use Case – Specific Functional Requirements

3.3 Non-Functional Requirements

Similarly, to the Functional Requirements described in the previous section, two main sets of non-functional requirements are provided in the following subsections. Those cover common non-functional requirements for the technologies to be developed, as well as specific requirements for each of the three use cases.

As a reminder, Non-Functional Requirements describe properties that the system functions must/should/may have. These typically include performance, scalability, usability, security and other qualitative requirements that may be defined or expressed in absolute or relative terms. For example, some performance requirements are expressed in absolute or relative terms. For example, some performance requirements are expressed with absolute terms using a specific number or property value (see e.g., ...), while others are expressed qualitatively in an effort to declare something less-easily quantifiable through a specific value.

This document covers the first increment of the requirements definition. As such, a number of features have not been implemented yet and experimentations and feedback are limited. Therefore, certain non-functional requirements are declared in the scope of this document and are expressed in relative terms. During the second increment of the document, they will be ratified and quantified more precisely.

Last but not least, in the Functional Requirements definition, each use case specific requirement is narrowly associated with a specific usage scenario (some applied to more than one). For the Non-Functional Requirements, the qualities described through them are broader than a specific use case scenario scene. Therefore, while there is a distinction between general and use case specific non-functional requirements, the non-functional requirements are broadly associated with use cases rather than specific scenarios.

3.3.1 General Non-Functional Requirements

The following Table 5 lists the non-functional requirements for the general technologies to be developed.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Status
GNFR1	The XR-HMIs must be functional during the whole activity of the machine	MUST	
GNFR2	The XR-HMIs must inform the human operator about a dangerous situation in a sufficient amount of time depending on the speed of motion.	MUST	
GNFR3	The XR-HMIs must be compatible with the embedded system inside the mobile machinery	MUST	
GNFR4	The design and development process must involve representative vehicle operators in all major design and evaluation activities and provide them with opportunities to influence design and development decisions for their respective use-case.	MUST	Updated
GNFR5	During the design and implementation of feature ideas and interaction concepts, the utility, usability, safety and positive user experience for the human operators should always be prioritized above conflicting interests, unless technical feasibility is not given, or privacy infringements are detected.	SHOULD	
GNFR6	The implementations of integrated XR technologies must apply access controls and authorization mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals or entities can access personal data	SHOULD	
GNFR7	Personal data, collected by integrated XR technologies should be protected through encryption techniques while stored, transmitted, and processed.	SHOULD	

GNFR8	The chosen XR technologies should apply the principle of minimisation, therefore only collect and retain the necessary amount of personally identifiable information, to fulfil its intended purpose.	SHOULD	
GNFR9	Privacy considerations must be integrated into the architecture and development processes of XR technologies; privacy-by-design must be a guiding principle; specifically: a) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing; b) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it	MUST	Updated
GNFR10	At least one concept for positive user experience must be integrated and tested in one of the final demonstrators.	MUST	Updated
GNFR11	The design of the overall system architecture should have the potential to be extended to support new/additional sensors, XR technologies or output devices.	SHOULD	
GNFR12	Each of the developed XR enhanced HMI features must increase operation performance, safety, usability, or user experience. It is our goal to achieve improvements in at least one of these criteria, but we strive to improve two or three at the same time with each of our our XR interaction concepts.	MUST	Updated
GNFR13	The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.	SHOULD	Added
GNFR14	Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.	SHOULD	Added
GNFR15	Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing about the use of this system.	MUST	Added
GNFR16	Where UX-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.	SHOULD	Added

Table 5: General non-functional requirements

Justification for updates:

- GNFR9: Specified, based on the results of project-related privacy requirements development (procedures and rationales are outlined in D2.3)
- GNFR13-16: Added, based on the results of project-related privacy requirements development (outlined in D2.3)

3.3.2 Use Case Specific Non-Functional Requirements

Table 6 presents the non-functional requirements associated with the specific use cases.

Requirement ID	Use Case	Description	Level	Status
UCNFR.1	UC2	When the human operator is controlling the reachstacker, the XR information and control commands should be received in real-time	SHOULD	
UCNFR.2	UC3	The displayed information and visualization must represent the actual situation with a maximal latency of 1s or clearly indicate an insufficient visualization.	MUST	

UCNFR.3	UC3	Any sensor or system function which is not operable must be clearly shown on the UI so that the operator can assess the system functionality.	MUST	
UCNFR.4	UC3	The system must be operable even if no sufficient GNSS signal is available.	MUST	

Table 6: Use case specific non-functional requirements

3.4 Technical Requirements

In the previous sections, the Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the technologies and use cases have been defined. According to this definition, these requirements cover the set of user-visible requirements, that is, they describe user visible functionalities and qualities that the technologies must, should or may provide. However, another set of requirements, named Technical Requirements, have also been identified. These requirements cover functionalities, organization, and architecture issues as well as technology features that are internal to the functioning of the different technologies to be developed. Although they are not visible to an external user, they are fundamental for the proper functioning of the technologies that are planned to be developed inside THEIA^{XR}. This section lists these specific requirements. Similarly, to the requirements described before, the Technical Requirements presented in the table below, have a unique associated ID (TR.#) to make them identifiable throughout the duration of the project, a requirement description, and a level characterization.

Requirement ID	Description	Level	Status
TR.1	The data communication interface with the haptic force feedback module(s) should support a high framerate and a low latency, i.e. frame-rate not lower than 250 Hz (ideally 1 kHz) and latency not higher than 4 milliseconds (ideally 1 millisecond). The data communication interface with the haptic vibrotactile feedback module(s) should perform with a framerate and latency at least on par with those of the visual feedback components.	SHOULD	Updated
TR.2	The haptic module must be able to operate in degraded mode without feedback in the event of a failure, and behave like a standard joystick.	MUST	
TR3	For integrating the visualization infrastructure and interaction system, a supply voltage range of 9V-32V must be available in the mobile machinery.	MUST	
TR4	XR solutions and/or applications that will be hosted on the visualization and interaction system will need to be developed in C, C++ or C#.	SHOULD	
TR5	Sensors and output devices should ideally have Ethernet and CAN interfaces to ensure proper interaction between the devices and the visualization and interaction system.	SHOULD	
TR6	The visualization infrastructure and interaction system must support industrially accepted communication busses (CAN, Ethernet) that are present in the mobile machinery	MUST	
TR7	Physical means will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to mount external equipment (e.g., rooftop mount for projectors, active lights and cameras)	MUST	

TR8	Electrical powering facilities and wiring options will be required for the individual off-highway machinery to power external equipment (e.g., up to 220V power rails for active lights and projectors)	MUST	
TR9	Existing sensor equipment and databases for individual off-highway machinery will provide already available data to the XR solution to be developed (e.g., proper localization information from GNSS, environmental models as meshes)	SHOULD	
TR10	To support the execution of XR technologies on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a Unity license for embedded linux platforms (arm64) has to be present.	MUST	Added

Table 7: Technical Requirements

Justification for updates:

- TR1: Distinguished requirements for force feedback (high constraints on framerate & latency) and tactile feedback (low constraints on framerate & latency).
- TR10: For the XR applications within the project to be executed on the embedded visualization and interaction system, a license of unity is mandatory as this is part of the execution environment.

4 Evaluation Criteria

This section describes the evaluation criteria defined in THEIA^{XR} Description of Action to measure the success of the project. The evaluation is based a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that aim to assess the project's performance and ensure it meets the main objectives that have been set for the project.

In the subsequent sections, the KPIs for each objective are going to be presented and described, providing insights on how each KPI is associated with the different technologies to be developed, how the achievements of every KPI are going to be measured and validated and which are the baseline performances that need to be matched or surpassed.

4.1 Objective 1: Increase of productivity, safety, responsibility and perceived presence

The first objective of THEIA^{XR} aims at the improvement of the productivity and safety of the human operator, but also to give the operator a sense of responsibility for the task at hand. The following KPIs will give a measure for the evaluation of this objective.

KPI-ID	1.1
Name	Improvement of safety for humans, equipment and cargo. We plan to identify and eliminate at least three common situations of human error or danger through design concepts. Perceived presence, awareness and responsibility will be measured in the status quo, these values need to be significantly surpassed by the prototypes.
Description	Common safety problems that put operators, equipment and/or bystanders at risk in the three use-cases will be identified and at least three concepts for their mitigation will be developed as part of the transdisciplinary co-design process. Situation awareness and responsibility will be measured for the status quo by collecting questionnaire results from operators based on their use case experience (see baseline). This measurement will be repeated with the THEIA ^{XR} prototypes, and the results compared. In the logistics use-case (UC2), where remote operation is intended for the prototypes, perceived presence will be assessed and compared to manual operation or, if possible, to remote operation of larger cargo cranes (in lack of a directly comparable remote operation scenario for reach stackers, where this is currently non-existent).
Lead Partner	HdM
Scope	Research on safety hazards in the work environment and subsequent development of concepts to increase safety is part of the context-of-use and threats analysis and the transdisciplinary co-design approach. The completed concepts will also be handed on to the technical development work packages of the project.
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Environmental hazards have been studied with an adaptation of the Critical Incident Technique (CIT). Results have been reported in D3.1/D3.6 and possible solutions have been described in the vision scenarios presented in D3.2. Possible solutions to increase safety are not limited to any specific technologies.
Means of verification	At least three hazard mitigation concepts must be co-evaluated and approved by the operators to confirm that they present a safety improvement in the respective use-case. Perceived situation awareness, perceived presence (only UC2) and perceived responsibility: The prototypes must significantly surpass the baselines in A/B studies comparing the status quo with prototype interaction. For perceived

	presence in the remote operation scenario (UC2), this only applies if a comparison with remote control desks of other harbour vehicles is possible.
Baseline	<p>Hazard mitigation concepts: No baseline needed, since the concepts will be co-evaluated with vehicle operators. Qualitative statements will be collected to validate the benefit of the concepts. Perceived situation awareness, presence and responsibility: Baselines will be collected from vehicle operators on comparable status quo situations via (adapted, if necessary) quantitative questionnaires in the third project year. The following questionnaires have been selected and partly already prepared for use, but may be adapted if deemed necessary in future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situation Awareness Rating Technique / SART [74] • ITC-Sense Of Presence Inventory / ITC-SOPI [75] • Responsibility Questionnaire / RQ [76]

KPI-ID	1.2
Name	Reassurance of intuitiveness and usability. Ease of use of the current machine operation modalities will be measured by questionnaires and user tests [73][77]. These values must be matched in our XR prototypes to ensure that the “virtual cabin” and its additional information and interaction modalities will not be detrimental to the ease of use.
Description	Usability and intuitiveness of vehicle operation will be measured for the status quo by collecting QUESI questionnaire results from operators based on their use-case experience. This measurement will be repeated with the THEIA ^{XR} prototypes, and the results compared.
Lead Partner	HdM
Scope	Research on usability, the development, testing and optimization of easily usable interface design and interaction concepts is part of the whole transdisciplinary co-design work package, as well as the technical design and implementation of the HMI.
Mapping technologies or methodologies	The design phase will use a scenario-based design approach, applied within the transdisciplinary co-design framework. The evaluation will involve HCD methods like usability testing and scientific questionnaires (like the QUESI), using prototypes of various fidelity levels, starting from simple written scenarios and paper prototypes up to partly implemented simulators.
Means of verification	The prototypes must significantly surpass the baselines in A/B studies comparing the status quo with prototype interaction.
Baseline	<p>Baseline will be collected from vehicle operators on comparable status quo situations via a quantitative questionnaire in the third project year. The following questionnaire has been selected and prepared for use, but may be adapted if deemed necessary in future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire for Measuring the Subjective Consequences of Intuitive Use / QUESI [73]

4.2 Objective 2: Increase of interaction quality

It is important that the usage of XR technologies will improve the interaction of the human operator and the machine. To evaluate this, different KPIs are defined that will validate this. The following KPIs will form the basis for the evaluation of the functionality and usability of the XR-based HMIs to be developed.

KPI-ID	2.1
Name	Utility of augmenting information in work task completion above conventional HMI functionality, evaluated through performance measures such as time on task, situational awareness and work quality
Description	THEIA ^{XR} aims at improving machine operation using advanced XR interaction techniques and technologies. This will subsequently lead to changes in functionality, look and feel of human-machine interfaces and force operators to adapt to such novel and unfamiliar systems. Superior utility is considered a vital benefit, capable to outweigh adaption costs for operators. In industrial applications, good utility refers to the extent to which technology helps the operator to successfully complete a task or to cope with a situation. Bad utility refers to a lack of benefit and result in unnecessary complexity and workload. The operator's perception of utility is situation-specific and depends on individual factors such as preferences, familiarity and expertise.
Lead Partner	TUD
Scope	Utility assessment is a part of Usability evaluation (see 2.2) with a special focus on ensuring a useful application of XR technologies and interaction techniques rather than an implementation based on “because we can”. This ensures that THEIA ^{XR} will focus on applying technologies and techniques that create real value within the use cases and beyond.
Mapping technologies or methodologies	Developing useful HMIs requires domain understanding and a requirement analysis that considers operators’ workflows, cognition, information use as well as task characteristics and contextual factors. Further, continuous involvement of stakeholders in our Co-Creation approach (WP3) ensures proficient and critical utility thinking.
Means of verification	Utility will be assessed using standardised Usability questionnaires that cover utility dimensions, as well as open questionnaires during co-creation and prototype-based testing phases.
Baseline	Comparative measures regarding operators' perception of conventional machine controls, questionnaire included baselines and results of existing measures in similar contexts [70][71][72] will be used as baseline.

KPI-ID	2.2
Name	Improved usability of XR interface design, evaluated through usability measures (e.g., SUS, and UEQ (aim: at least reach a “good” evaluation on the pragmatic scales according to the benchmarking by [58]).
Description	Usability is a fundamental and well elaborated quality criterion of interactive systems. Usability includes several factors, such as efficiency, effectivity, intuitiveness, satisfaction and utility. Assessment of Usability therefore gives a good impression of how operators perceive a certain HMI in terms of operation performance, interaction performance and resulting personal experience. Usability assessment nowadays often goes along with measuring other user experience factors and workload as these often relate to each other. Requires interactive scenarios and interactive prototypes.
Lead Partner	HdM, TUD
Scope	Assessment of overall usability proves general quality of our developed solutions and whether operators tend to want to work with them or not. Continuous measurement of usability and its factors during development on feature level also guides a focused development towards valuable solutions for future HMIs.

Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Same as in 2-2.
Means of verification	Usability will be assessed using standardised questionnaires (SUS, UEQ+, etc.) open questionnaires, and observations during co-creation and prototype-based testing phases.
Baseline	Operators' perception of conventional machine controls will be used as baseline. Usability is measured with absolute and relative items that refer to this existing experience

KPI-ID	2.3 & 2.4
Name	Better predictability of system behaviour, evaluated through observation and user questionnaire & Improved comprehensibility of system behaviour evaluated through observation and user questionnaire.
Description	As digital data processing, assistive services and automation increase and displays gain in complexity, maintaining system transparency is already an issue in high-spec off-highway machinery. An HMI's intelligibility is a central feature and indicator of system predictability. Even though THEIA ^{XR} also aims at reducing complexity, providing high levels of system transparency is a requirement for the HMI features that will be developed.
Lead Partner	TUD
Scope	Measurement of predictability is very complex and difficult as it requires a sufficient familiarization or mental model of the user interface on the operator side. required time for suitable familiarization requires extensive experiment designs that are not feasible for iterative development procedures. Instead THEIA ^{XR} focuses related factors, that are easier to assess. Such factors that indicate good predictability are intuitiveness and usability which will be also measured with standardized questionnaires in combination with qualitative feedback.
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Predictability in terms of HMI functionality and design relates to its capabilities to develop accurate mental models within the users. Thus, the simpler an HMI is or behaves the easier it is for operators to understand its working and the faster operators reach a level of good system predictability. High levels of HMI familiarity and Intuitiveness might also support perceiving high levels of system predictability. Using familiar interaction techniques can help to outweigh the use of novel interaction technologies that are unknown to the operators so far.
Means of verification	Predictability related factors usability and user experience, comprehensibility and trust and system dependability will be assessed using standardised questionnaires (e.g., SUS, UEQ+, etc.) in a highly interactive prototype capable to simulate real working conditions on a reasonable level.
Baseline	Evaluation of HMI features, developed in THEIA ^{XR} , will utilize Eiband's Transparency Design Guidelines Error! Reference source not found. and Hoffman's Explainable AI Metrics Error! Reference source not found.

KPI 2.3 and 2.4 are merged in this overview as the underlying factors predictability and comprehensibility are highly related within the overall experience of the XR interaction technologies. These are assessed together but will be discussed separately in the overall system performance evaluation.

4.3 Objective 3: Development of advanced multi-modal interaction technologies

THEIA^{XR} aims to investigate and develop XR technologies that can be applied to the off-highway domain and explicitly to the use cases targeted in the project. Different technologies and approaches will be investigated

with various measures required. The following KPIs will target those and will provide the measures for success of these technologies.

KPI-ID	3.1
Name	10% faster and accurate Calibration and Registration Techniques as most common commercial library in indirect viewing scenarios research and developed; prototype ready for testing.
Description	<p>Different modalities for sensing the environment and visualizing information require the use of advanced registration and calibration methods. Interestingly, for a group of domains, algorithms to perform calibration do not even exist to date. An example for this is a panoramic thermal camera, for which no approach is known to date.</p> <p>This leads to a slight redefinition of the objective in the sense that we need to invent new algorithms for such device configurations overall, subject to investigations regarding accuracy and precision in a scientific context, with a validation in the specific applications in the individual use cases.</p>
Lead Partner	TUG
Scope	All Use Cases
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Thermal Imaging, LIDAR Cameras, Projection-based Visualization, Active moving Lights/Cameras
Means of verification	Scientifically valid experiments and corresponding documentation and publication in scientific venues. Verification by means of practical experiments within the industrial environment of the individual use cases.
Baseline	The current baseline is that neither the sensor assemblies built, nor the respective calibration or registration methods are generally available; at the end of the project a set of hardware prototypes and corresponding control software will be available.

KPI-ID	3.2
Name	Transcoding and Visualization, respectively conveying on non-visible data to the user researched and developed; prototype ready for testing
Description	<p>The rough environmental conditions (i.e., zero-sight conditions, limited visibility around the machinery,) require new ways to visualize information. The use of head-worn hardware for mostly prohibitive as the working conditions do not allow wearing such devices for a longer period of time. As opposed to the lab- or consumer-driven AR using head-worns, we require alternatives to provide information, subject to redefining the technological type of AR/XR used throughout the project.</p> <p>In order to enlarging the possibilities for visualization, the aim is to use projection-based AR setups, including Laser Projection, the use or image-based (or a-priori knowledge based) object detection, motorized light spots to be combined with the registration of the machine within the environment and implementing specific functionality in order to convey information.</p>
Lead Partner	TUG
Scope	All Use Cases
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Laser Projection, Motion-controlled Spotlight, 3D Reconstruction and Mapping, Surface visualization (Meshing), Panoramic Imaging

Means of verification	Scientifically valid experiments and corresponding documentation and publication in scientific venues. Verification by means of practical experiments within the industrial environment of the individual use cases.
Baseline	Fragmented approaches for very special visualization or transcoding mechanisms exist in the literature, but no software packages exist to provide coherent functionality; at the end of the project a set of software utilities fitting the developed prototypes will be available.

KPI-ID	3.3
Name	Advanced novel 3D space visualization multimodal UI concept for natural interaction, including haptic and acoustic feedback to enhance the immersion beyond the visible spectrum; prototype ready for testing.
Description	Enable improved environmental visualization in a remote control environment that allows no direct visibility to work site. Effects of VR and AR technologies like real-time virtualization of the scene will be investigated during the project. Concept will be developed and evaluated with end-user during development by exploiting human-centred methods.
Lead Partner	VTT
Scope	Improve feeling of immersion and precision of control through higher quality and natural environment visualisation.
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Utilization of sensor information (camera) to achieve better situational awareness will be studied. The contribution of force-feedback based on a dynamic model of the environment will be investigated. Additionally, end-to-end latency time and reliability of the communication with wireless 5G mobile network are investigated carefully during the project.
Means of verification	Increasing performance of remote-controlled operation compare with normal manual operation from the cabin. Increasing productivity and decrease ergonomics related sick leaves with better usability and situation awareness.
Baseline	Subjective – operator experience and expectations, reported feeling of control, safety, and productivity.

KPI-ID	3.4
Name	Highly accurate registration between virtual and real information in a location sensitive context, irrespective of the user MR visualization technology (VR vs. head-word AR vs Display); prototype ready for testing
Description	The tele operation system of the remote control environment connects a physical machine in a real work environment with a purely digital twin that is used by the operator to assess work conditions. High accuracy is especially important with regard to the correct alignment of position, sizes, distances and movement speed of objects within the work area.
Lead Partner	TUG
Scope	Real-time detection of the environment with high accuracy requires highly accurate registration between virtual and real information. Dynamics of environment includes, moving vehicle, moving objects, and moving persons.
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	DGPS-Integration over CAN-Bus, Thermographic Imaging, Spotlight Object/Person Targeting, Rudimentary DL-based Object/Obstacle/Person Detection, Laser-Projection-Based AR, Panoramic Cameras
Means of verification	Subjective Operator Judgement, Scientifically Valid Evaluation Tests
Baseline	Approaches in the literature for the developed prototypes exist only for stationary setups, yet not for moving machinery; the results of the project will include

	prototypical implementations for the individual visualization prototypes deployed on moving machinery.
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KPI-ID	3.5
Name	Operational concept of multimodal immersive control cockpit, implemented and demonstrated on at least two use cases.
Description	The control cabin of an off-highway machine always calls upon several modes of interaction (one thinks for example of audible alarms and head-up displays), but in a very crude way. One of the major challenges of the project is to manage to integrate several XR technologies inside a cockpit to achieve a truly operational immersion. The problems to be solved relate to ergonomics (avoiding conflicts between sensory channels), calibration techniques (guaranteeing the consistency of information between the modalities), system architecture (ensuring the delivery of data without latency), and software (providing high-performance interfaces).
Lead Partner	HAP
Scope	Use Cases 1, 2 and 3
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Stereoscopic visualization Haptic feedback
Means of verification	Immersive cockpit technology framework implemented and integrated into two selected use cases.
Baseline	The current baseline is that no multimodal immersive cockpit is available, and at the end of the project one will be available.

4.4 Objective 4: Ensuring humane workplaces

THEIA^{XR} aims to provide technologies to ensure humane workplaces by taking the requirements from the human operator into close consideration (related to Objective 2). As humans are closely involved in the design, development, and evaluation phase, we also have to take into consideration the data privacy related to these topics. The following KPIs are associated with the effort to achieve those goals.

KPI-ID	4.1
Name	Identify privacy principles to be fulfilled in the design solution, leading to measurable privacy and UX outcomes, measured for instance with UEQ, meCUE or similar. The objective will be to iteratively improve the solutions, leading to positive outcomes for both UX and privacy perceptions. Where available, we will use benchmarks from these tools to evaluate our comparative UX and privacy outcomes (e.g., [58][63]).
Description	The objective is to identify privacy and ethical requirements that must be addressed in the design solution, leading to measurable improvements in both privacy and user experience (UX). To measure UX, we intend to use the UEQ privacy subscale as it provides a benchmark for evaluating the user experience of the proposed system solutions. To comprehend user concerns about the privacy of our system, we plan to utilize the Users' Perceived Systems' Privacy (UPSP) method. Additionally, we will apply the Sentence Completion Method and series of interviews to gain insights into how users perceive privacy risks associated with different types of data.
Lead Partner	UL
Scope	Quantitative and qualitative methods to access users' perception of privacy in XR-enhanced workflow.

Mapping technologies or methodologies	to or	Privacy-by-design methodology, Value sensitive design methodology, Humanity-Centered Design Methodology, Extended TAM model, Linddun Go privacy and security risks elicitation approach.
Means of verification		Results of the UEQ+ scale should show the above average results compared to UEQ+ KPI-based benchmark data for privacy scale (TRUST scale), MUIPC scale, adapted to measure concerns with XR implementations (more about determined baseline can be found in the “Baseline” section); the combined results of UPSP and qualitative methods should demonstrate that end-users and stakeholders understand and accept the privacy controlling mechanisms, used in the proposed solutions (agree with proposed solutions, can name benefits of the solutions for their work, know which data are collected, agree with this collection). All additional personal data collection beyond the industrial baseline should be justified and privacy preserving mechanisms proposed.
Baseline		<p>Current state of art in the UC industries about data sharing, data storage and data usage, collected via expert interviews (described in D3.3). The solutions aimed not to provide more privacy risks as they existing now and if possible introduce more privacy-preserving approaches.</p> <p>We propose the following baseline for quantitative validation: UPSP (Ayalon Toch 2019) scale will be used to perform high-level evaluation of the full XR-enhanced vehicle (with all implementations).</p> <p>As there is no existing benchmark for the questionnaire, we decided to based it on original data(no higher than 4 by all subscales (institutional setting,)) by 7-point Likert scale will indicate the low level of privacy concerns; up to 5 will be considered as acceptable level. [64]</p> <p>Based on previous studies, provided received statistics for parameters [65] [66][67]), we decided to apply the following baseline: Not higher than 4 in 7 point Likert scales (“Neither Agree nor Disagree”) for each of the parameters of Perceived surveillance, Perceived intrusion and Secondary use of information. However, as the scale is adopted from the other domain (Mobile Apps), the final results should be discussed in the broader context, taking into account the qualitative measures of user's understanding (what is the nature of privacy concerns about the technology, do user clearly understand which information the XR feature collect). The scale is applied by each implemented feature separately (e.g. object detection, XR-supporting cameras for distant operation etc.); the final list of features will be determined on the integration step</p> <p>TRUST UEQ+ scale: There is no specific benchmarks for UEQ+ scales, however based on previous literature, general rating between +1 and +2 can be considered as good level of UX [68], when everything on "positive" side (more than 0 on -3 to +3 scale) will be considered as acceptable (following [69]); The scale is applied by each implemented feature separately (e.g. object detection, XR-supporting cameras for distant operation etc); the final list of features will be determined on the integration step.</p>

KPI-ID	4.2
Name	Improvement of quality of work through psychological need fulfilment and positive experiences at work. Measurement of the need fulfilment [62], and specifically self-efficacy and meaningfulness of work, in the current work environment and in prototype/demonstrator. We aim for a perceived increase of at least one point on average in the respective scales for at least two psychological needs.
Description	Perceived psychological need fulfilment will be measured for the status quo by collecting questionnaire results from operators based on their use-case

	experience, especially focusing on self-efficacy and meaningfulness. This measurement will be repeated with the THEIA ^{XR} prototypes and the results compared.
Lead Partner	HdM
Scope	Research on user experience and the design of positive experience concepts will be part of the whole transdisciplinary co-design work package, as well as the technical design and implementation of the HMI.
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	This research and development will mainly affect the HMI, its information architecture and interaction design, but also possibly extend to the development of dedicated technical features of the XR systems.
Means of verification	The prototypes must significantly surpass the baselines in A/B studies comparing the status quo with prototype interaction
Baseline	Baselines will be collected from vehicle operators on comparable status quo situations via (adapted, if necessary) quantitative questionnaires in the third project year. The following questionnaires have been selected and partly already prepared for use, but may be adapted if deemed necessary in future: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Self-Efficacy scale / GSE [59] • User Needs Scales / UNeedS [61] • Work And Meaning Inventory / WAMI [60]

4.5 Objective 5: Design, implement and validate a set of real-life use cases target new domains

Under the specific objective, the goal is to demonstrate, validate and evaluate the technologies developed inside the THEIA^{XR} project in the three use cases: snowgrooming, logistics and construction. The KPIs that are provided below are used as a measurement to assess the success of this effort.

KPI-ID	5.1
Name	Validation of THEIA ^{XR} in three different use cases, each in relevant real-world environment and with real-life data.
Description	Integration of methodologies and technologies from WP3, WP4 and WP5 into the use case demonstrators. Deployment, testing and demonstration of implemented THEIA-XR methodologies, technologies and applications with the actual demonstration environment by utilizing real-life demonstrators.
Lead Partner	PRIN
Scope	Snowgrooming, Container handling with Reachstacker and Construction machinery
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Potentially all developed technologies within the project. Particularly all technologies assembled or simulated.
Means of verification	Depending on the use case, with surveys, interviews and technical measurements
Baseline	Identified technologies integrated into the mobile machinery, tested and validated on the functionality. The focus in this part is mainly on the technical functionality of the systems, if their technical performance is similar or better as was described in the technology specification. Baseline therefore is that currently no technologies are available in the machines and at the end of the projects, these technologies are integrated into the machinery and tested on functionality.

KPI-ID	5.2
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Name	Identification of at least 2 different new application domains to deploy THEIA ^{XR} solutions
Description	Contact created and discussion started with other off-highway or other application domains where potentially the results of THEIA ^{XR} can be deployed in the future. Ideally, these companies will provide a Letter of Interest for following the results of the projects and continue potential cooperation with the partners after the end of the project.
Lead Partner	TTC
Scope	Co-Design framework / XR-based human-machine interaction
Mapping to technologies or methodologies	Potentially all developed technologies within the project.
Means of verification	Discussion started with companies/institutes outside the consortium and potentially a Letter of Interest (LoI).
Baseline	As baseline, the already three available Use Cases (snow grooming, logistics and construction) are used, as these are already available inside the project so investigate on the usability and applicability of the developed technologies. The aim is to interact with as many other domains (but at least two) to look beyond the domains identified inside the project.

5 Conclusions

The final version of this deliverable D2.5 – Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification captures the work that has been carried out within Task 2.2 of the THEIA^{XR} project. The main goal of this task is to capture the state-of-the-art of methodologies and technical solutions targeted within the project, thus aiming at XR technologies and off-highway mobile machinery, but also on the co-design methodology developed and deployed within the project. Additionally, it provides the baselines for the technologies and where our developments will go beyond state-of-the-art. These expectations are captured through the requirements specifications, namely the specifications of Functional, Non-Functional and Technical Requirements, set by the human operators but also by the technology developers.

This is the reason that the requirements are providing in such close cooperation with the use cases. The use cases are built upon user feedback and technology enablement. For this increment of the document, user feedback is mostly provided by the industrial partners of the project, whose R&D and commercial activities are in the field of off-highway applications and are engaged with real customers. The first increment of this deliverable (D2.2) was based on initial research, planning activities and initial user feedback. For this increment of the deliverable, the development work that has been carried out as part of the first phase of the project is taken into consideration and therefore adjustments and updates based on the first phase research and development work as well as more extended external user feedback is taken into consideration. This is the reason that certain original requirements have been added, updated or removed.

Along with the requirements, the updated evaluation criteria have been reiterated and updated since the first increment (D2.2), taking into account the first actual evaluation process that has been carried out in Task 6.3 and reported in the deliverable D6.3. The sets of KPIs that are specified in this document are going to shape the final evaluation process that will be carried out once all development and integration work has been completed in order to provide the final assessment of THEIA^{XR}. An update of the baselines has also been provided to ensure a proper validation of the results.

With the completion of the final version of this deliverable marks the end of Task 2.2 and with that the end of Work Package 2, so all the specifications, requirements and baselines have been defined. This deliverable, including deliverable D2.4, set the stage for the forthcoming activities that will lead to the final versions of the prototypes and demonstrators to be developed within the project. Based on the updated specifications and requirements, the final versions are going to be provided. This work will steer the research and development activities of Work Packages 3, 4, 5 and 6 and will be the basis for the final validation and evaluation of the results of the project.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AUI	Adaptive User Interface
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
CIT	Critical Incident Technique
CMS	Camera Monitoring System
CPS	Container Positioning System
CPU	Central Processor Unit
DGM	Digitale Geländemodelle
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCD	Human-Centred Design
HCI	Human Computer Interaction
HMD	Head-mounted Displays
HMI	Human-Machine Interaction
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display
MI	Multimodal Interaction
MR	Mixed Reality
NUI	Natural User Interface
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
QUESI	Questionnaire for Measuring the Subjective Consequence for Intuitive Use
RC	Remote Controller
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SA	Situation Awareness
SART	Situation Awareness Rating Technique
SDK	Software Development Kit
TOS	Terminal Operating System
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
UI	User Interface
UPSP	Users' Perceived Systems' Privacy
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality
WAMI	Work and Meaning Inventory
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality
XRSI	X Reality Safety Intelligence